

Linnæus University

Sweden

Master's Thesis

The Flavour of Words

A Study of Standardised Vocabularies and How
Olfactory, Gustatory and Haptic Attributes in Wine
Reviews are Currently Rendered in English

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Abstract

This study delves into the intricacies of the language used in wine reviews, focusing on the adoption of standardised wine vocabularies, specifically the original Wine Aroma Wheel (Noble A. C. et al., 1984) and the Wine Lexicon of the Wine and Spirit Education Trust (WSET Level 4 Systematic Approach to Tasting Wine®, 2023). It investigates the extent to which professional wine reviewers adhere to these standard lexicons or opt for individualistic expression. An essential component of the research identifies and analyses emerging terms in wine reviews, shedding light on the evolving nature of wine discourse. The study's findings indicate that while standardised vocabularies are influential and foundational, there remains room for individualised expression in conveying the nuanced sensory experience of wine tasting. Additionally, the research highlights the importance of these emergent terms and their potential to enrich existing wine vocabularies. Given the global nature of the wine industry, the study underscores the need for a more inclusive and adaptive linguistic approach. To this end, the research suggests the potential benefits of a controlled vocabulary system tailored for the wine sector. Despite its inherent challenges, such a system could streamline wine descriptions, promoting a more consistent understanding across diverse audiences along with better communication among professionals.

Keywords

aroma, controlled vocabularies, cultural inclusivity, flavour, oenology, sensory experiences, standardised vocabularies, wine discourse, wine reviews, wine tasting

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background and Significance of Wine

The production and consumption of wine have a long history, deeply intertwined with the cultures and religions of most Western societies, earning it a reputation as a distinguished beverage. Since the 1980s, interest in wine has been expanding to a much broader demographic, a phenomenon attributed by scholars to increased disposable income among individuals and a shift in perception of wine as a work of art rather than just a food item (Hommerberg, 2011; Hommerberg & Paradis, 2014; Stearns, 2016). Wine as an object of distinction denotes social status and refined taste. The language used to describe wine, with its focus on sensory perceptions and tasting notes, further reinforces its status as a refined and sophisticated beverage. The appreciation of wine is also seen as a sign of cultural capital. Knowledge about wine and its production is considered a mark of education and refinement. Wine can also be considered a work of art, due to the intricate procedures involved in its production and the distinctive sensory sensations it provides. The creation of wine involves a delicate balance of factors. These include the selection of specific grape varieties, the quality of the soil and climate, as well as the employment of particular fermentation and ageing techniques. Each step in the winemaking process is meticulously interwoven to produce a unique final product, much like a painter's canvas or a composer's score. The sensory experience of wine also has artistic elements, as the tasting of wine can involve the appreciation of a complex range of flavours, aromas, and textures. The appreciation of wine as a work of art is also demonstrated by its valuation and collection, where uncommon and exceptional wines hold substantial value and are pursued by collectors and connoisseurs alike. In this way, wine can be seen as a multifaceted work of art that appeals to the senses and reflects the talent and skill of its creators. Accordingly, the acquisition of knowledge regarding wine has recently gained increasing significance in affluent countries globally (McCoy, 2005; Silverstein, 2003). The increased interest in this subject has been addressed by numerous sources, including books, films, magazines, and websites (Caballero et al., 2019). In addition, a vast amount of scholarly research has been conducted to examine the topic of wine from various perspectives, such as agricultural, chemical, geographical, sociological, and linguistic. Within these contexts, wine discourse emerged as a genre.

1.2 The Linguistic Challenge, Controversies and Standardisation Efforts in Wine Terminology

One of the most important aspects of language development is the production and adaptation of vocabulary related to the description of daily-life experiences and objects. The linguistic landscape reflects the inherent creativity of languages, which are endowed with the ability to generate novel lexemes and re-purpose pre-existing ones, in order to address emergent conceptual requirements. The human perception of the world is closely interconnected with the five senses - vision, hearing, touch, taste, and smell. These sensory modalities are fundamental to our perception of and interaction with our environment, and language serves as a medium to convey and

communicate these experiences and impressions to others. There is an intricate relationship between sensory experience, cognition, and language, with the former exerting a significant influence on the latter. However, empirical studies have demonstrated that the five perceptual modalities (visual, haptic, auditory, olfactory, and gustatory), are not equally represented in English, and other Western languages. Instead, visual perception is found to be prevalent, while taste and smell are comparatively underrepresented (Winter, 2019). It has also been found that the olfactory and gustatory modalities are multisensory domains, thus they are interconnected and supplement each other, especially when it comes to food and drink (Lynott & Connell, 2009).

In wine discourse, the limited representation of olfactory and gustatory stimuli in the English language creates significant challenges stemming from the need to accurately and effectively communicate sensory experiences related to wine tasting. As a result, wine discourse and particularly wine critics must rely on vocabularies from other domains, such as botany or chemistry, as well as figurative language, to convey the desired sensory impressions. As Caballero and Suárez-Toste (2008) explain, in a world where wine is rapidly evolving into a cultural icon within an emerging hedonistic sub-culture accessible to a larger consumer base than ever before, the absence of metaphorical language would render wine virtually undiscussable.

However, this approach caused a debate as to the value and accuracy of such descriptions. According to some scholars, wine reviews are ineffective in communicating the flavour/taste profile of wines. This notion is exemplified by the opinions of Quandt (2007), who suggests that the wine industry is susceptible to misleading claims and attracts individuals who engage in such practices. Similarly, Shesgreen (2003) argues that wine reviews are written in obscure language by authors who lack a genuine understanding of the wines they are describing. Additionally, Lawless' (1984) experimental study supports this view, showing that the language used by wine experts in their descriptions is highly idiosyncratic, with most terms used only once by a single expert. At the other end of the spectrum, research showed that wine experts exhibited consistency in their descriptions (Croijsmans & Majid, 2016; Hendrickx et al., 2016). Perhaps a way to better understand the reasons behind this controversy would be through Jackson's (2009, pp. 226-233) distinction of wine experts as "Experience-based experts" and "Training-based experts". Accordingly, the first group refers to sommeliers and wine writers, having extensive practice in assessing the quality of different types of wine. They tend to use emotive language to describe wines, which is idiosyncratic and varies greatly among individuals. The vocabulary these experts use to describe things is relatively narrow, and there's not much consistency in the terms they employ. The second group includes members of sensory analysis panels and university-trained winemakers. They use a standard lexicon of descriptive terms that refers to specific reference samples with which they have been trained. In their case emotive language is discouraged in favour of objective, standardised language. Some of these specialists might possess significant experience with identifying the attributes that could define unique wine types, regions, or styles, while others might not.

The limitations of everyday sensory vocabulary, in a developing wine industry, necessitated the establishment of systematic terminologies for describing wine, especially its flavours, to foster shared understanding within the community of experts. The initial effort to standardise wine descriptors was developed by oenologists from the University of California Davis (Noble et al., 1984). That first Wine Aroma Wheel (hereinafter WAW), as it is known from the graphic representation of the scheme, is focusing on descriptors primarily limited to objects. It uses a categorical and hierarchical system (e.g., Pineapple and Banana are co-hyponyms of the hyperonym Tropical Fruit, which itself is a hyponym of Fruity), excludes subjective, hedonic terms, (e.g., well-rounded, rich, young, old, balanced), and attempts to be as specific as possible. Several other wine wheels followed that example. The Wine and Spirit Education Trust (WSET) (What we do, n.d.), an educational foundation for professionals and enthusiasts, originally established in the UK, in 1969, nowadays a global organisation, proposed an alternative approach. The WSET approach introduced a schema of descriptors for Appearance, Nose (smell), and Palate (taste and mouthfeel), organised along scales (Table). Currently several wine vocabularies exist but the present study will focus on the two previously mentioned, as they are deemed to embody the most comprehensive and representative approaches.

Along with the burgeoning appreciation of wine as a beverage of distinction, a cultural marker and work of art, a concomitant demand for wine reviews was observed, a phenomenon that can also be associated with e-commerce (Kana, 2023). Wine reviews are brief texts primarily intended for consumption by the general public, written by professional wine critics or experts. The reviewer's essential task is to convey the essence of the sensory experience in a manner that is comprehensible and enticing to the reader. To undertake the reviewing process successfully, a reviewer must possess extensive knowledge in various domains related to wine production and consumption. Moreover, the reviewer must possess exceptional sensory abilities to discern the subtleties of the four key perceptual modalities in wine tasting (visual, haptic, olfactory, and gustatory), and the holistic impression resulting from the sensory input that evokes an aesthetic response. Finally, the reviewer's ability to communicate this experience through language is crucial to their credibility among consumers and, consequently, their professional success (Hommerberg, 2011; Hommerberg & Paradis, 2014; Paradis & Hommerberg, 2016). More precisely, the wine tasting process consists of a visual as well as an olfactory and a gustatory evaluation. The initial phase of wine tasting, the visual examination, assesses the wine's colour, clarity, age, and weight. This evaluation starts by looking straight down into the glass to get a sense of the depth of colour, density, and saturation of the wine. Holding the glass to the light and tilting it allows one to see the complete colour range, including the wine's edges, which can provide clues about the grape variety and aroma. The side view reveals the wine's clarity and any sediment or fermentation problems, while the tilted view offers insights into the wine's age and weight. Swirling the glass provides an opportunity to observe the formation of "legs" or "tears", which indicate the wine's alcohol and glycerine content. Their presence is associated with a wine likely to be fuller-bodied, denser, and with a more mouth-filling texture. Swirling also aerates the wine in the glass and releases its aromas. In the stage of the olfactory

assessment, the taster sniffs around the glass, first to inspect if there are any off-aromas, such as cork, burnt matches, vinegar, nail polish, or yeast, indicating flaws. Then they look for all the other aromas they can perceive. The olfactory evaluation is then enhanced by the gustatory assessment, during which the taster takes a small sip of wine into their mouth and moves it around in a way that it can release its aroma and coat in the mouth (Gregutt, 2015). Next, they assess the aftertaste of the wine, in other words, the taste and aroma that remains in the mouth after swallowing or expectoration, and finally, the finish which is the overall impression of the wine's taste, texture and complexity as it leaves the mouth.

1.3 Research Aims and Objectives of the Current Study

The present study aims to analyse a specific sub-genre of wine discourse, specifically, wine reviews (WR) written by experts. Wine critics assess and describe wines for an audience interested in staying informed about wines, using these reviews as a point of reference for future purchases or to compare professional assessments with their own personal experiences (Caballero et al., 2019, p. 30). In this study the term “standardised vocabularies” refers to a set of terms that a particular community of users has collectively agreed upon. The use of standardised vocabularies in wine reviews enhances clarity and facilitates effective communication of wine experiences. Given that the development of a standardised wine vocabulary is an ongoing process, this study aims to investigate whether the existing vocabularies are comprehensive or if further enhancements are necessary. The research questions addressed in this study are as follows:

RQ 1: Do the wine reviews adhere to a standardised set of terms from the WAW and WSET vocabularies? If wine reviews do follow a standardised set of terms, which vocabulary, WAW or WSET, is more frequently used? Are there also other terms incorporated in wine reviews, in addition to the standardised terms?

RQ 2: Do the reviewers display consistent linguistic patterns, or the results of RQ1 could be influenced by the idiolect of certain reviewers?

RQ 3: What are the main terms that reviewers use in addition to the WAW and WSET vocabularies (referred to as “NULL” hereafter)? Does their frequency suggest a need for further expansion or completion of the standardised vocabularies?

The study will be based on a public-domain dataset from Kaggle (Datasets, n.d.), consisting of all wine reviews from Wine Enthusiast (About us, n.d.), for the years 2017-2020. The wine reviews were conducted through blind tastings by 19 expert wine tasters, either editors of the magazine or other knowledgeable panellists.

In order to answer RQ1, three sensory vocabularies were assembled for control. The first two, referred to as WAWvoc and WSETvoc, were based on the Wine Aroma Wheel by Noble et al. (1987) and the Systematic Approach to Tasting by the Wine and Spirit Education Trust, respectively. The third vocabulary, DATAvoc, was

created ad hoc based on the wine reviews in the dataset being analysed. The data were processed with various codes in Python and analysed with Excel, resulting in a comparison of term frequencies in DATAvoc with WAWvoc and WSETvoc respectively, as well as a list of frequent terms beyond the two standardised vocabularies.

For RQ2, the linguistic behaviour of the reviewers was observed by creating nineteen sub-corpora of reviews, with each one consisting of a random sample of 145 reviews from each of the nineteen reviewers of the original dataset. The sub-corpora were processed with various codes in Python and analysed with Excel, resulting in a comparison of term frequencies, in a similar way as they were previously, for RQ1. The outcomes from each reviewer were compared to the results of the entire corpus to see if any specific patterns emerged.

Qualitative along with quantitative methods were implemented to answer RQ3, as the NULL terms were found to be a significant proportion of the total (i.e., 26.31%). More precisely, the collocations of the top NULL tokens were checked, in order to limit the analysis to the tokens related to wine flavours. Further qualitative analysis took place to understand why reviewers used these additional descriptors. The findings of this investigation can indicate whether the standard vocabularies need to be expanded to include the additional descriptors or whether the NULL terms do not add any meaningful information.

2 Background and Literature Review

From antiquity to our days, wine has always been considered a beverage of distinction as well as a central component of social gatherings and religious ceremonies in most Western societies. It can be considered one of the most heterogeneous types of food due to several factors. Firstly, there is a multitude of grape varieties, each with its own unique aromatic and taste profile. Secondly, environmental and traditional factors, such as climate and terroir, impact the flavours of the produced wine. Additionally, winemaking techniques, including the use of different yeasts, fermentation methods, and ageing processes, play a significant role. Lastly, the age of the wine is another element that affects its flavour. It is equally heterogeneous and complex from a sociological perspective, as Demossier (2004) suggests, and it cannot be understood as an ordinary commodity, because historically it always conveyed a sense of prestige, and still contributes to the hierarchisation of society.

2.1 Humanity and the Evolution of Wine

Wine is loaded with symbolic meanings and has been an important part of religious and social rituals across various cultures and time periods. Evidence from the Hittite texts and the Epic of Gilgamesh, as well as from archaeological findings show that the peoples of Mesopotamia used wine for rituals and festivals (Powell, 2003; Unwin, 2005, pp. 63-66). The consumption of wine in Egypt was considered a symbol of prestige and was primarily reserved for the upper classes and the royal family. Wine had a significant role in the daily temple rituals and was also included in funerary offerings. Additionally, wine was employed in medical treatments during that era (Guasch-Jané et al., 2013). In New Kingdom Egypt, several Canaanite Jars, produced in different regions, display inscriptions on their sidewalls documenting their contents. These inscriptions, written in hieratic script, provide information beyond the mere contents of the vessels. They also identify the vineyard's location, the vintner's name, the year of vintage, which is often denoted by the pharaoh's reign, and occasionally detail the type of wine, quality, and sweetness (Lesko, 2003). Some of them also include information about their ownership, indicating whether they belonged to the royal, temple, or private domain (Uncorking Egypt's wine heritage, 2016). In ancient Egypt, as well as in Mesopotamia, beer was the main alcoholic beverage while wine was reserved for consumption by kings and priests. (Unwin, 2005, pp. 55-59). In classical Greece, wine held significant value as an aristocratic beverage, as well as an offering to the gods. Moreover, it was considered a valuable trade commodity, requiring specialised techniques and labour-intensive processes for its growth and production. Despite the limited extant evidence for the Greek Bronze Age, textual analysis of Linear B documents reveals that a similar perspective to that of classical Greece was present (Palmer, 2003). The grapevine held a symbolic significance and was linked to the deities Dionysus in Greek and Bacchus in Roman mythology. Dionysus, who was venerated as the god of wine, fertility, and theatre, was often portrayed as a liberator who emancipated individuals from their repressions and associated with unbridled and euphoric conduct. Similarly, Bacchus, the god of wine and fertility of the fields, was frequently depicted as a genial figure who imparted happiness and

delight into people's lives and was also associated with untamed and ecstatic behaviour. The worship of both Dionysus and Bacchus was encompassed by an aura of mysticism. In Judaism, wine is included in the ceremonies of Shabbat and Pesach. Within the Christian faith, wine serves as a symbol during the Eucharist or Communion, where it represents the blood of Jesus Christ. Nevertheless, the provision of wine to the laity during the Mass has been a contentious issue for the church, due to its limited availability and elevated expense (Unwin, 2005, pp. 118-121). In Islam the consumption of alcohol is forbidden in this world due to its intoxicating properties however, in the allegory of Paradise, rivers of wine are promised to the pious, among other delights (The Qur'an, 2004, p. 332). Throughout history, wine has been employed as a symbolic representation by various cultures, and in each succeeding generation, additional layers of meaning and significance have been attributed to it. Despite these changes, wine has consistently held an important position as a symbol of cultural values and beliefs.

During the eighteenth century, the growing urban population in Europe drove an increased demand for affordable and low-quality wine. At the same time, the aristocracy sought to differentiate themselves from the masses by creating new and unique types of wine, like champagne and clarets, which served as symbols of their status and refinement. These wines were often produced in small quantities and marketed to a select clientele, emphasising their exclusivity and luxury. The divergent trend in the wine industry was marked not only by the mass production of low-quality wines but also by a substantial amount of falsification and corruption. Although wine "treatments" had been in use for centuries, during the seventeenth century, the practice began to take on fraudulent qualities with the addition of substances such as sulphur, isinglass, egg whites, and colourings. This use of additives and adulterants served to mask the inferior quality of the wine and increase profits for unscrupulous producers and merchants. In response, various regulatory measures were introduced to combat these fraudulent practices, including labelling requirements and the establishment of quality control standards. One of the main attempts was demarcating a wine region. The establishment of a hierarchical system of estate classification in these regions was largely based on the prices that the wines could command. The goal was to create a system that provided consumers with assurance of the authenticity and quality of the wines they were purchasing, while simultaneously promoting the interests of the landowners. The classification system established by courtiers in 1855 played a significant role in setting the prices of wines, as the status of a property greatly influenced its value. This system created a hindrance for new wine estates to emerge and ensured that the top-ranked properties in the classification maintained their high prices.

In the late nineteenth century, vineyards throughout Europe were afflicted by a variety of fungal and insect parasites, including the devastating Phylloxera which originated in North America. Phylloxera (*Phylloxera vastatrix*) is an aphid-like insect that attacks vine roots causing damage and ultimately killing the plant. Its arrival caused an unprecedented crisis, as the pest rapidly spread throughout Europe, destroying entire vineyards and causing extensive economic harm (Unwin, 2005, pp. 236-273). The discovery of a cure for phylloxera was a lengthy process, and to this day, efforts to combat the pest continue as it possesses a high degree of resistance and a constantly adapting genome (Rispe et al., 2020). Three methods

were more successful in addressing the problem. One was the use of chemicals which however had harmful effects on the environment and human health. Another was experimenting with crossing grape varieties to create new hybrids resistant to phylloxera while still producing wines that were palatable to European tastes. The hybridisation process involved two types of hybrids: direct-production ones, obtained by crossing two or more different American vine species, and French hybrids resulting from the crossbreeding of European and American vine species (Meloni & Swinnen, 2013). The resulting hybrid grapevines inherited the phylloxera resistance from the American parent and some of the desirable characteristics of the European parent. Nevertheless, the process was not without controversy, as some wine purists argued that the resulting wines were inferior to those produced from traditional European grape varieties (Gale, 2011, pp. 201-210). The third method involved grafting native vine scions onto resistant American rootstocks. The resulting social and economic impacts of the phylloxera crisis were profound. Although larger producers were able to absorb the increased costs of the new techniques, small-scale producers were forced to abandon their farms. In the long run, the phylloxera crisis laid the foundations of modern viticulture. However, at the time, an immediate effect was the reduction in wine supply and a subsequent surge in fraudulent activities such as the adulteration of wine with chemicals or blending it with wines from other regions.

By the turn of the 20th century hybrid grape varieties and grafting had allowed the French vineyards to be progressively reconstructed and production to recover. However, the producers could not compete against the prices of international products and fake wine made with raisin and sugar that were flooding the market, which led to serious protests. In response, the government heavily taxed imports and focused on protecting the authenticity and quality of French wines through the creation of appellations. The Appellation d'Origine Contrôlée (AOC) system, is a French regulatory framework that seeks to protect the reputation of regional wines by controlling the geographical origin, grape varieties, and production methods of the wine (Teil, 2010, pp. 253-274). AOC forbids hybrids from inclusion in wines labelled with an appellation but allows grafting. According to Laporte (2001), the AOC system helps to reduce information asymmetry in the market for quality wines by providing consumers with credible signals of quality and by incentivizing producers to maintain high standards of production, thus successfully promoting the reputation of French wines and supporting the development of regional wine industries. Several other wine-producing countries followed the example of France, as:

1. USA, with American Viticultural Area (AVA) (American Viticultural Areas (AVAs), 2022)
2. Italy, with Denominazione di Origine Controllata (DOC) and Denominazione di Origine Controllata e Garantita (DOCG).
3. Spain, with Denominación de Origen (DO) and Denominación de Origen Protegida (DOP)
4. Portugal, with Denominação de Origem Controlada (DOC) and Vinho Regional (VR).
5. Germany, with Qualitätswein bestimmter Anbaugebiete (QbA) and Prädikatswein.

6. Greece, with Appellation of Origin of Superior Quality (AOSQ).

The AOC system laid the foundations for the current wine policy in Europe, which primarily focuses on a system of appellations in the form of geographical indications (GIs). This system involves extensive technological regulations, including restrictions on permissible grape varieties, maximum yields per hectare, and guidelines for grape production and winemaking procedures (Alston & Gaeta, 2021). Since its implementation in 2009, the Common Market Organisation (CMO) reform has regulated the entire wine production chain and categorizes Quality origin wines into Protected Designations of Origin (PDOs) and Protected Geographical Indications (PGIs) (EFOW - EU rules applicable to origin wines).

As mentioned earlier, the impact of the phylloxera crisis on viticulture was transformative, paving the way for the quality-focused, organised practices in modern viticulture. Traditional practices of planting vines in a haphazard manner and taking cuttings from the same vine (layering) were replaced by more systematic approaches, such as trellising and orderly row planting. This allowed for the implementation of horse-powered machines and, eventually, mechanisation. Only the best plots were chosen for replanting, leading to a marked improvement in the quality of wine produced and the virtual end of table wine production. Additionally, the crisis led to a more effective organisation of vineyards, further enhancing the efficiency of grape cultivation (Raynolds, 2022; Skelton, 2020).

2.2 The Boom

A trend of growing interest in wine began in the 1970s and increased significantly in the 1980s, has persisted to the present day and can be attributed to a variety of factors. Some of them were related to innovations in production, namely in viticulture, vinification, and supply chain. Other factors were associated with socioeconomic and cultural reasons. More specifically, changes in the viticultural and oenological parts of the production chain were accompanied by quality regulations and a transport revolution. The production has shifted away from being primarily composed of small, family-owned businesses with a traditional outlook and a focus on Europe, to a more diverse industry dominated by multinational corporations. These transformations have led to a greater emphasis on ensuring quality and consistency (Aylward, 2005). The Judgment of Paris, a blind taste competition held in 1976, revealed that Californian wines were of exceptional quality. This event marked a significant turning point in the wine industry, as it forced the international community to acknowledge New World wines as a high-quality alternative to the dominant European brands. The competition challenged the longstanding belief that European wines were inherently superior and helped to establish the reputation of California wines as a leading force in the global wine market (Taber, 2005). The emergence of new players in the global wine industry, along with the resulting increase in the availability and affordability of wine, has broadened access to this beverage, making it more accessible to a wider range of consumers. On the socio-economic and cultural side, Howland (2022) argues that the neo-liberal reforms of the 1980s onwards have made the consumption of quality wine a symbol of cosmopolitan refinement for the global middle class, who share common desires for economic affluence, education, urban living, and upward mobility. Under this favourable climate, the wine industry opened up to a wider

audience through increased visibility and accessibility. This has been made possible by the presence of wine in supermarkets and the proliferation of advertisements, newspaper columns, and social media marketing. The availability of affordable table wines in supermarkets has contributed to the democratisation of wine, allowing lower- and middle-income consumers to get acquainted with different wine varieties without incurring significant costs. This has enabled consumers to acquire a greater understanding and appreciation of different wines, leading to an increased demand for diverse wine varieties. However, while the democratisation of wine has brought it within reach of more people, it has not prevented the social stratification in certain contexts. As wine enthusiasts and high-income consumers sought out superior products and services, they began gravitating towards exclusive wine vendors that focused on the upper echelon of the market and provided specialised services beyond the capabilities of larger retail chains and supermarkets (Loftus, 1985; Unwin, 2005, pp. 273-315). During the period when wine was categorised into two distinct types, namely, fine wine intended for the rich and low-quality table wine, consumers did not need wine reviews to help them make their choice. However, after the democratisation of wine, a middle ground of very good wines at affordable prices has emerged, appealing to the middle classes.

2.3 Wine Reviews

Wine appreciation has evolved into a cultural phenomenon that encompasses not only consumption and commercial transactions but also the pursuit of knowledge and understanding about this noble beverage. This pursuit of knowledge has become essential for those who want to be perceived as socially sophisticated and well-informed (Wislocka Breit, 2013), and is partially due to the growth of wine journalism in the 1980s, (Unwin, 2005, pp. 273-316) which has provided wine enthusiasts with access to more in-depth and accurate information about wines from around the world.

As a result, wine reviews or tasting notes (another term for wine reviews) have become a prime source of information for many consumers, helping them discover new and exciting wines to try. According to Robinson (2015), Wine reviews are written records produced by professional or serious wine enthusiasts. They typically comprise descriptions and evaluations of the appearance, aroma/bouquet, taste, and overall conclusion of the wine. Wine reviews are short in length, usually up to 100 words depending on the complexity of the wine being tasted. They can be found through a variety of mediums, including daily newspapers, lifestyle magazines, online sources, descriptions attached to wine bottles, and commercial advertisements and their purpose varies depending on the medium on which they are published. Hence, three types can be distinguished: Promotional wine reviews, whose communicative objective is to convince consumers to purchase the advertised product; Wine reviews on wine bottles, which aim to declare the contents and provide information to the buyer; and wine critics' wine reviews, which, in addition to the informative function, evaluate the specific wine and offer guidance to the readers about their future consumption choices (Hommerberg, 2011). The present study is focusing on the third type as it can be considered the most standardised one. The complexity of wine appreciation can make it difficult for consumers to know which wines will meet their expectations, and many of them are hesitant to rely

solely on their own taste preferences. Instead, they turn to wine critics to assist their choice of product. Wine critics have developed into a profession, and consumers in non-producing countries rely heavily on their recommendations, leading to a shift in power relations from producers to critics. The choice and appreciation of wine can function to position consumers with respect to their social identity, as wine selection is often seen as a marker of taste and cultural refinement (Hommerberg, 2011). To fully comprehend the structure of a wine review, it is essential to have a firm grasp of the wine-tasting procedure, as described in Figure 1.

Each sample should be poured into identical, clear, tulip-shaped, wine glasses. They should each be filled (1/4 to 1/3 full) with the same volume of wine.

I. Appearance

- 1 - View each sample at a 30° to 45° angle against a bright, white background.
- 2 - Record separately the wine's:
 - clarity (absence of haze)
 - color hue (shade or tint) and depth (intensity or amount of pigment)
 - viscosity (resistance to flow)
 - effervescence (notably sparkling wines)

II. Odor "in-glass"

- 1 - Sniff each sample at the mouth of the glass before swirling.
- 2 - Study and record the nature and intensity of the fragrance* (see Figs 1.3 and 1.4)
- 3 - Swirl the glass to promote the release of aromatic constituents from the wine.
- 4 - Smell the wine, initially at the mouth and then deeper in the bowl.
- 5 - Study and record the nature and intensity of the fragrance.
- 6 - Proceed to other samples.
- 7 - Progress to tasting the wines (III)

III. "In-mouth" sensations

(a) Taste and mouth-feel

- 1 - Take a small (6 to 10 ml) sample into the mouth.
- 2 - Move the wine in the mouth to coat all surfaces of the tongue, cheeks and palate.
- 3 - For the various taste sensations (sweet, acid, bitter) note where they are perceived, when first detected, how long they last, and how they change in perception and intensity.
- 4 - Concentrate on the tactile (mouth-feel) sensations of astringency, prickling, body, temperature, and "heat".
- 5 - Record these perceptions and how they combine with one another.

(b) Odor

- 1 - Note the fragrance of the wine at the warmer temperatures of the mouth.
- 2 - Aspirate the wine by drawing air through the wine to enhance the release of its aromatic constituents.
- 3 - Concentrate on the nature, development and duration of the fragrance. Note and record any differences between the "in-mouth" and "in-glass" aspects of the fragrance.

(c) Aftersmell

- 1 - Draw air into the lungs that has been aspirated through the wine for 15 to 30 s.
- 2 - Swallow the wine (or spit it into a cuspidor).
- 3 - Breathe out the warmed vapors through the nose.
- 4 - Any odor detected in this manner is termed aftersmell; it is usually found only in the finest or most aromatic wines.

IV. Finish

- 1 - Concentrate on the olfactory and gustatory sensations that linger in the mouth.
- 2 - Compare these sensations with those previously detected.
- 3 - Note their character and duration.

V. Repetition of assessment

- 1 - Reevaluate the aromatic and sapid sensations of the wines, beginning at II.3—ideally several times over a period of 30 min.
- 2 - Study the duration and development (change in intensity and quality) of each sample.

Figure 1. Sequence of wine tasting
Note: From (Jackson, 2009, pp. 2-3)

2.4 Communicating Sensory Experiences

As Goode (2007) notes, the term *wine tasting* is inaccurate because this activity engages not only one but four of the human senses, vision, olfaction, taste, and touch (mouthfeel). Wine tasting requires exceptional sensory abilities as well as extensive knowledge in wine production and sensory evaluation to discern and communicate the full sensorial spectrum of the tested wine to the consumer (Paradis & Hommerberg, 2016). It is widely recognised that, particularly in Western society, vision holds a special significance, surpassing other senses in terms of reliability and objectivity (Hommerberg, 2011). Viberg (2001) notes that when faced with conflicting auditory or tactile information, humans tend to depend heavily on their visual perception, even in situations where the visual input may be misleading. According to Levinson and Majid (2014), the prevalence of vision as the primary human sense has resulted in the development of language that is more responsive to visual distinctions. This dominant role of vision is believed to account for certain linguistic patterns, including the greater frequency of visual words (San Roque et al., 2015). Consequently, an asymmetry between the senses is mirrored in an asymmetry between words (Winter, 2016). In the domain of sensory perception, olfaction and gustation stand out as senses that are notoriously challenging to describe with words. This difficulty in describing sensory experiences is referred to as *ineffability*. Although our enjoyment of food and beverages is greatly influenced by our perception of taste and smell, effectively expressing these senses through language is often challenging. The inability to fully describe these experiences stems from the subjective and fluctuating nature of sensory perception, given that smell and taste can vary significantly from person to person, as well as among different cultures (Levinson & Majid, 2014). Describing wine is not just about the product itself and its chemical composition, it involves the taster's cognitive processes, in other words the mechanisms that the human brain uses to acquire and apply knowledge. Therefore, wine-tasting involves the taster's prior knowledge, memory and emotions associated (Parr, 2019).

The lexicon available in English and most other Western languages to delineate olfactory and gustatory perceptions is restricted. This suggests that the challenge individuals face when trying to label smells and tastes may be influenced by their *WEIRD* (Western, Educated, Industrialised, Rich, Democratic) background (Croijmans & Majid, 2016; Henrich et al., 2010). As a result, wine experts are compelled to rely on the utilisation of descriptions and *metaphors* to communicate those traits to their audience (Croijmans et al., 2020; Croijmans & Majid, 2016; Hommerberg & Don, 2015). The metaphors employed in wine discourse are not merely decorative devices, in fact they serve as an indispensable means of conveying the sensory experience of tasting wine and the perspective of wine specialists to others (Caballero & Suárez-Toste, 2008). In other words, metaphors serve as a bridge, addressing the inherent limitation in capturing olfactory and gustatory perceptions through language. Their employment facilitates effective communication, connecting the sensory encounter of wine tasting with its linguistic representation. The intricacies of the diverse array of flavours, aromas, and textures found in wine elude direct articulation, and thus metaphorical language becomes a means of conveying these experiences by drawing upon comparisons to familiar and relatable concepts. However, the combination of figurative speech and evaluative

lexis in wine reviews, which aims to emphasise positive or negative sentiments, can introduce elements of exaggeration and subjectivity. As a result, it is not uncommon for wine reviews to be met with scepticism.

Peynaud (1996) raises questions about the limits of sincerity in describing smells and flavours, suggesting that there may be elements of autosuggestion and bluff involved as mental expectations about a particular smell or flavour can affect the perception of it. For example, if someone reads a wine review that describes a particular wine as having notes of blackberry and vanilla, they may be more likely to perceive those specific aromas when they taste the wine themselves. Their expectation of those flavours can influence their sensory experience, even if the wine does not actually possess those exact characteristics. This can happen because the human brain is actively trying to match sensory inputs with expectations, leading to a confirmation bias. The same can happen by the power of suggestion from others.

M. Gluck (2003) presents a distinct categorization of wine writers, highlighting two primary types. The first group focuses on delving into intricate winemaking processes and skilfully constructing narratives, relying on vivid imagery rather than metaphorical language. The second group initiates their evaluation based on the sensory experience of consuming wine. However, these critics encounter linguistic challenges, as metaphors often become repetitive, and the vocabulary of wine inadequately describes abstract concepts. Gluck further notes that the world of wine criticism is frequently plagued by pompous snobbery and exaggeration, which has resulted in the satirisation of wine culture.

According to Quandt (2007), there is a notable lack of clarity and agreement among commentators when it comes to wine evaluations and descriptors. Quandt further emphasises the inherent ambiguity present in wine descriptions, which he aptly refers to as the “bullshit factor” and suggests that this ambiguity poses a hindrance to consumers’ ability to make well-informed choices, as wine writers often resort to inflated or unhelpful language. Furthermore, Quandt highlights the absence of a consensus among wine writers regarding the quality of wines, resulting in evaluations that are both unreliable and subjective.

In the observations made by Gawel (1997), the level of training that a taster has obtained may influence the language that they use to describe the taste and characteristics of wine. Specifically, he argues that trained tasters tend to use vague and abstract cues like oakiness, full-bodied, and tannic while untrained ones tend to focus on more concrete ones such as fruitiness, acidity, and sweetness. Sharing a similar perspective, Suárez-Toste (2007) and Caballero (2007) support the notion that the metaphorical language used in wine descriptions suggests that wine experts’ prose is unclear and overly literary.

Solomon (1997), on the contrary, contends that experts are more precise and detailed than novices in their descriptions of wines because their prior knowledge of wine regions and production techniques is also an essential component of wine expertise on top of a high level of sensory sensitivity and acuteness, allowing them to detect and discern the subtlest flavours, aromas, and textures in wines.

In the ongoing discussion regarding the evaluation of wine, sceptics often propose utilising science and technology as a means for assessing the traits and quality of wine. However, despite various attempts to quantify the characteristics and flavours of wine constituents through techniques such as gas chromatography and chemical analysis, the most widely accepted approach for accurately assessing the sensory attributes of wine remains tasting. Brochet and Dubourdieu (2001) highlight that while these scientific methods provide valuable information about the physicochemical structure of a wine's complex molecular composition, they fall short in capturing the full sensory experience of wine. Tasting wine involves the intricate construction of flavour in the taster's brain, which encompasses multiple attributes and engages various components of an individual's sensory abilities. This complex perception cannot be fully captured or replicated by analysing the wine's molecular composition alone. Thus, tasting remains the universally accepted approach for evaluating the sensory qualities of wine, as it encompasses the subjective and holistic experience that science and technology alone cannot encapsulate.

Just as food can stimulate memory and imagination, wine can also evoke memories and engage the imagination through its sensory qualities. When describing wine, individuals often rely on their recollection of past experiences with similar wines or related flavours and aromas. These memories can shape their perception and interpretation of the wine in question. For instance, while tasting a particular wine, someone may detect hints of blackberries and oak. This sensory experience can trigger reminiscences of picking blackberries in their grandmother's garden or recalling a previous occasion when they enjoyed a wine aged in oak barrels. Such memories and associations can add depth and richness to the wine-drinking experience, establishing connections to personal narratives and emotions. Descriptions of wine can draw upon these cognitive processes, engaging with memories and inviting the imagination to enhance the understanding and appreciation of a wine's characteristics (Forrest & de St. Maurice, 2022).

Additionally, individuals with diverse backgrounds often have unique interpretations and descriptions of wine aromas and flavours, influenced by their cultural context and culinary experiences. Cultural background plays a crucial role in shaping taste preferences, tolerance levels, and reference points when evaluating wine. As a result, it significantly impacts how people perceive the aromas, flavours, and textures of wine. For example, Asian cultures with a tradition of consuming bitter teas and vegetables may have a higher tolerance for elevated tannins in wine compared to Western cultures. Furthermore, the preference for savoury flavours over sweet ones in Asian cuisine can influence how Asian wine enthusiasts perceive and appreciate the flavours in wine. Asian tasters may also rely on familiar food and dining habits as reference points when assessing wine, drawing comparisons to textures, subtleties, and flavour profiles they are accustomed to (Cho Lee, 2009).

2.5 Towards a Standardised Vocabulary

Over the years, numerous wine glossaries have emerged as sections of wine books, trying to educate the public about the meaning of certain terms in wine descriptions, as well as serving as common points of reference among experts. In the 1970s, Lehrer (1975) conducted an extensive analysis of the vocabulary used in the domain

of wine tasting, examining both its internal structure and practical application. The findings revealed the intricate nature of wine language, stemming from the wide range of interpretations and the inherent challenge of achieving consensus on its meaning. In fact, the author challenges the notion of imposing scientific precision on wine descriptions and suggests that establishing a standardised vocabulary may not be necessary. Lehrer recognises the subjectivity involved in evaluating wine and emphasises the use of diverse language by different individuals. The study demonstrates how personal experiences and preferences shape the perception of wine and the choice of descriptive words. Therefore, the author argues that the individuality expressed in wine descriptions is an inherent part of the wine-drinking experience, making the imposition of a standardised vocabulary potentially undesirable or unfeasible.

However, following the 1980s boom, the necessity for a standardised wine vocabulary became increasingly apparent as a means for communicating wine experiences to various individuals within the wine industry for the following reasons:

1. **Communicating with Consumers:** Wine experiences need to be effectively communicated to consumers by sommeliers, merchants, and journalists. By using a technical language and specific terms, these professionals can convey the sensory attributes of wines accurately. This helps guests and consumers make informed decisions about wine selection and enhances their overall wine experience.
2. **Personnel Training:** In the wine industry, it is crucial to train personnel, such as sommeliers and waitstaff, to have a comprehensive understanding of wines. Using a technical language allows trainers to effectively convey information about different wines, their characteristics, and how to evaluate them. This ensures that personnel can confidently assist guests and provide excellent service.
3. **Creating Wine Lists:** Wine lists are essential in restaurants, wine bars, and other establishments serving wine. They help customers navigate the available wine options. A tool for communicating wine experiences enables sommeliers and merchants to describe wines accurately and vividly, allowing customers to make informed choices based on their preferences.
4. **Evaluating Wine and Food Combinations:** Wine and food pairing is a crucial aspect of the culinary experience. A tool for communicating wine experiences helps sommeliers and professionals in the food industry evaluate which wines complement specific dishes. By using a common language to describe the sensory attributes of wines, they can suggest suitable pairings that enhance the flavours and overall dining experience.
5. **Branding Wine:** Wine producers and marketers rely on effective communication to build and promote their wine brands. By utilising a technical language, they can describe the unique characteristics, quality, and sensory experience associated with their wines. This allows them to differentiate their products in a competitive market and effectively target their desired consumer base.

6. **Communication Among Professionals:** Wine journalists and other industry professionals rely on a common language to communicate with each other. By using specific terms and concepts, they can share their experiences, insights, and evaluations of wines accurately. This facilitates the exchange of knowledge, fosters critical discussions, and contributes to the overall growth and development of the wine industry.

While the earlier endeavours may not have been as methodical or explicitly concentrated on creating a universally accepted wine terminology, they established the groundwork for subsequent discussions and progress. The efforts of wine experts, the impact of regional wine classification systems, and the contributions of critics and writers all played a role in the gradual evolution of wine terminology. It is noteworthy to mention three experts who have exerted significant influence in shaping the landscape of wine tasting notes, each leaving their distinctive mark in the field. Robert M. Parker, Jr., is known for his 100-point rating system and is considered “the most influential critic of all times” (Hommerberg, 2011). Parker’s approach can be defined as “hedonic wine criticism” and it emphasised on the sensory pleasure derived from drinking wine. Within this framework, he introduced a distinctive vocabulary for evaluating and describing wines holistically, employing a standardised language with adjectives like “rich”, “powerful”, “opulent”, “juicy”, etc. Parker has faced criticism for the perceived limitations of his vocabulary however he has influenced numerous other wine critics. Michael Broadbent is known for his literary style and use of metaphor in wine descriptions. Ann Noble, a professor in the Department of Viticulture and Enology at the University of California, Davis, developed the Wine Aroma Wheel (James, 2018). While there is a consensus on the importance of a standard wine vocabulary, it is worth noting that the development and adoption of such standards can vary across regions and organisations. and there is no universally utilised one. This study will specifically focus on two widely known and influential standardisation systems: the Wine Aroma Wheel (WAW) and the Wine and Spirit Education Trust (WSET).

The first Wine Aroma Wheel (WAW) was developed in 1984 by the Sensory Evaluation Sub-committee of the American Society for Enology and Viticulture. Its primary objective was to establish a standardised set of wine aroma terminology, aiming to foster effective communication within the wine industry. The wheel operated on a hierarchical system comprising three tiers, with the initial tier encompassing generic terms, while subsequent tiers delved into greater specificity. By adopting this system, the wheel permitted analytical descriptions of wine aromas employing objective and non-evaluative language. It systematically grouped similar aroma characteristics together, utilising appropriate hierarchical terms to facilitate swift identification and description. However, it was acknowledged that certain circumstances required combining descriptors or employing more general terms when the utmost precision was unattainable. In order to facilitate the establishment of precise wine aroma terminology, the Sensory Evaluation Sub-committee additionally formulated a comprehensive set of reference standards. These standards were established either through the utilisation of chemicals or by introducing the appropriate product into a neutral base wine. For instance, to create reference standards for vanilla or apricot, a minute amount of vanilla extract or apricot nectar, respectively, was meticulously incorporated into a neutral base wine (Noble A. C. et

al., 1984). The 1984 WAW was modified in 1987, to further clarify and improve the original list of standardised wine aroma terminology (Noble A. C. et al.). This was an endeavour to develop a consistent and clear descriptor system and several other aroma wheels followed drawing on this model.

The Wine and Spirit Education Trust (WSET) introduced a schema of descriptors organised into Appearance, Nose, and Palate categories, each with its own scales. This schema incorporated object descriptors from the Aroma Wheel, encompassing both the smell (nose) and taste/mouthfeel (palate) dimensions. It is important to note that the WSET schema did not render Aroma Wheels obsolete; instead, it regarded them as complementary methodologies and analytical systems that could serve as useful guiding tools. The WSET schema aimed to provide a structured framework for describing wine characteristics, facilitating more precise and standardised communication within the wine industry. By offering a systematic approach to wine tasting, WSET courses equipped students with the skills to perform a comprehensive analysis of the attributes present in a wine. The methodology utilised pre-marked alternatives and separate terminology for wine types when judging appearance, while also considering previous experience or knowledge of the wine in the analysis process (Caballero & Paradis, 2013; Herdenstam et al., 2009). This study will specifically concentrate on the olfactory and gustatory/tactile dimensions of wine evaluation, thereby excluding the aspect of visual inspection from its scope.

It is important to acknowledge that the development of a standardised wine vocabulary is an ongoing process, continually evolving as new regions emerge, winemaking techniques advance, and consumer preferences change. Within this framework the present study will aim to observe which standardised vocabulary wine reviewers tend to use most frequently, specifically focusing on the WAW and WSET methods. Furthermore, the study will evaluate whether these two methods adequately address the expressive needs of the wine reviewers and identify any additional terms or descriptors that may be necessary to enhance the existing standardised vocabularies used in wine reviews.

3 Methodology

3.1 Purpose and Aims

Wine discourse is a unique genre that encompasses olfactory, gustatory, and tactile impressions as its defining characteristics. However, language lacks specific terms to effectively communicate these impressions, which introduces uncertainty. This has led scholars to engage in an ongoing debate concerning the informative nature of wine reviews, prompting the need for further investigation. To address this, significant efforts have been made towards the establishment of standardised vocabularies. This study focuses specifically on two major standardised vocabularies, WAW and WSET, aiming to examine how sensory attributes are conveyed in wine reviews and to what extent. Moreover, it seeks to uncover the use of terms outside of these standardised vocabularies and understand the underlying reasons for their employment. The study will also analyse the language usage patterns of each reviewer, to discover whether all reviewers follow the same pattern, or if individual linguistic style, or idiolect, of some reviewers influences their reviews. Each individual native speaker possesses a unique idiolect that is reflected in the way they use language in both spoken and written forms. This idiolect is shaped by their personal experiences and influences and is manifested through their distinct choices in both spoken and written forms (Coulthard, 2004). Lastly, the study aims to investigate the potential reasons behind the use of words outside of the standardised vocabularies if such usage is observed. The part of WSET that pertains to “Appearance”, in other words to the visual inspection of wine, will be disregarded as it falls outside the scope of this research.

In the past, the humanities, particularly social sciences, and sociolinguistics, used to create a divide between *Qualitative* and *Quantitative* methods, resulting in an epistemological chasm (Walby, 2001). However, a new methodological approach called *Mixed methods* emerged in the late 1980s and 1990s as an alternative to this dualism. It combines both methods into a single study, utilising various techniques for data gathering, analysis, research designs, and question types. By combining statistical and thematic analysis methodologies, researchers can seamlessly switch between the two (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009). As suggested by Punch (1998), researchers should consider the research question and the specific context of the project before deciding on an approach. Methodological decisions should be determined by the substantive focus of the research, rather than the other way around. To investigate the use of the standardised vocabularies in wine discourse, this study will employ a mixed-methods approach. The rationale behind this decision is that combining both procedures can potentially reveal more information than using them separately. While quantitative methods can provide information on language use, they cannot offer insights into the underlying motivations for that usage (Bijeikienė & Tamošiūnaitė, 2013). To address the “why” question, qualitative measures may be necessary. This triangulation of methods will not only validate individual findings but also enhance the understanding of the topic by highlighting its unique features and nuances (Kana, 2023).

3.2 Data Description

3.2.1 Original Source of the Dataset

The present research is based on a dataset obtained from Kaggle, a public dataset repository. The owner of the data is Valeriy Mukhtarulin (nd) who built it using the original scraper by Zack Thoutt (2017) to obtain fresher data. According to Mukhtarulin, the dataset includes all wine reviews from winemag.com for the years 2017-2020 with duplicates removed. The winemag.com database is maintained by Wine Enthusiast, a major magazine about wine, published by Wine Enthusiast Company in Valhalla, New York. The magazine has a readership of 800.000 people worldwide. The wine reviews in the database are updated by a team of experts who taste more than 24.000 wines from across the world every year. The dataset consists of a total of 81.116 entries in tabular format, each one including information about

- 1 The country of origin,
- 2 The review,
- 3 The designation,
- 4 The rating,
- 5 The price,
- 6 The province of origin,
- 7-8 Two more levels of origin information,
- 9-11 The taste's name, photo, and link to their Twitter account,
- 12 The name of the wine,
- 13 The variety
- 14 The vintage, and
- 15 The winery

3.2.2 Ethical Considerations Regarding the Dataset

This study adheres to the principles of academic integrity, transparency, and ethical conduct, ensuring responsible use of the data and respect for the reviewers' work. The dataset utilised in this research is based on a public-domain (CC0) dataset obtained from the public dataset repository on Kaggle. The winemag.com database is widely recognised as a trusted source within the industry. The wine reviews included in the database are authored by expert reviewers who are identified by their names in the magazine. The findings and conclusions drawn from the dataset are presented in a thoughtful and aggregated manner, duly acknowledging the valuable contributions made by the named reviewers. The research ensures transparency and responsible data utilisation, honouring the expertise and efforts of the reviewers.

3.2.3 Preparation of the Dataset and General Remarks

The dataset was assembled into a corpus to fit the purpose of this study, keeping the information about:

- 1 The country of origin,
- 2 The review,

- 3 The province of origin,
- 4 The taster's name,
- 5 The name of the wine,
- 6 The variety,
- 12 The vintage,
- 13 The winery

The dataset consists of various vintages, and it is worth noting that a few of them are not correctly mentioned in the vintage column. However, the vintage has been considered of minimal importance for the purpose of this study, as it focuses on the terms that the tasters use to describe wine. The reviews documented in the dataset are based on blind tastings, meaning that the reviewers are unaware of the producer or retail price of the individual selection being assessed. The wines are typically tasted in groups consisting of 5-8 similar items. Although the reviewers possess general information about the flight, such as the vintage, variety, or appellation, the identities of the products are kept concealed to prevent any bias from influencing the evaluation. If a wine is identified as flawed or outside of expected parameters, it is retested as feasible. The reviewers are 19 expert wine tasters, either editors of the magazine, or other knowledgeable panellists, and each review is the result of an individual evaluation or in a collective setting.

One issue encountered with the corpus of data relates to the presence of special characters from European languages (á, é, í, ó, ú, ä, ö, ü, ß, à, è, ì, ò, ù, â, ê, î, ô, û, č, š, ž, ā, ē, ī, ō, ū). To address this problem, three different encodings were attempted: UTF-8, ISO-8859, and Latin-1. Among these, Latin-1 performed better than the other two, but none of them eliminated the issue. This suggests that the dataset may contain various encodings if the scraping process was not standardised or systematic. This is not uncommon in datasets obtained from repositories. To confirm this assumption, Code 1 (Appendix 6) was utilised, revealing at least three different encodings: ASCII, ISO-8859-1, and Windows-1252. Trials were conducted using Code 2 (Appendix 6), and it was ultimately decided to use "Windows-1252" as the original encoding for the entire dataset, as it provided better results although not completely resolving the problem. The output file was encoded in "UTF-8." Manual corrections were made to address remaining issues, including spelling errors (e.g., "phenoloc," "phneolic" instead of "phenolic," "sagebursh," "sagebrush," "pineapplle" instead of "pineapple," etc.). Additionally, different spellings of the same word were left untouched. To ensure consistency in grape variety labelling, different names used for the same grape were amended to a single name. For example, "Shiraz" was changed to "Syrah," "Pinot Nero" to "Pinot Noir," etc. Words with prefixes such as "ultra-," "super-," "under-," and "un-" were treated as if they were without their prefixes. For example, "ultraclean" and "superfresh" were counted as 'clean' and 'fresh', respectively. Furthermore, reviews that did not include the reviewer's name were excluded.

3.3 Data Processing and Tests Performed

3.3.1 RQ 1:

Do the wine reviews adhere to a standardised set of terms from the WAW and WSET vocabularies? If wine reviews do follow a standardised set of terms, which vocabulary, WAW or WSET, is more frequently used? Are there also other terms incorporated in wine reviews, in addition to the standardised terms?

To address these questions, three sensory vocabularies involving olfaction and gustation were compiled. The first vocabulary, referred to as WAWvoc (Appendix 2), was created based on the Wine Aroma Wheel developed by Noble et al. (Appendix 1). The second vocabulary, known as WSETvoc (Appendix 4), was based on the Systematic Approach to Tasting by the Wine and Spirit Education Trust (WSET) (Appendices 3a and 3b). These two vocabularies were used as standardised references for control. The third vocabulary, DATAvoc (Appendix 5), was specifically developed by analysing the reviews of the dataset. The purpose of DATAvoc was to capture all the possible descriptors for aromas and flavours used in the dataset.

The assembly process for WAWvoc involved gathering all the terms from the Wine Aroma Wheel (WAW) and compiling them into a tabular file. Multi-word terms were split into individual words.

WSETvoc was assembled by extracting terms from the WSET Level 4 Wine-Lexicon, which serves as a support for the WSET Level 4 Systematic Approach to Tasting Wine (SAT) (2022). This vocabulary encompasses clusters and descriptors for Primary, Secondary, and Tertiary aromas and flavours. The assembly process for WSETvoc followed the same procedure as for WAWvoc.

The assembly process for DATAvoc involved multiple steps. Firstly, the corpus of wine reviews underwent pre-processing using a Python code (Appendix 6, Code 3). This pre-processing included tokenization, punctuation removal, and stopword removal. Concurrently, the frequency of appearance for each token was recorded. Subsequently, the list of tokens resulting from the pre-processing step underwent manual review. The objective was to select only those tokens that were most likely to be used as descriptors of aroma and flavour in the wine reviews. The result was saved in file "DATAvoc_frequency.csv" and includes the tokens corresponding to aromas/flavours and their frequencies of appearance in the dataset.

Then, CODE 4 (Appendix 6) was employed to generate a table. This table comprises three columns: the first column includes the words extracted from "DATAvoc_frequency.csv", the second column records their frequency of appearance, and the third column indicates whether each word corresponds to WAWvoc or not. The same procedure was repeated for WSETvoc.

The original strategy entailed using stemming on both the vocabulary words and the corpus of the reviews. This approach aimed to streamline data analysis by reducing words to their root forms, thereby treating variations of the same word, such as

'acid,' 'acidic,' 'acidity,' and 'acids,' as equivalent. However, the Porter Stemmer and Snowball Stemmer did not yield the expected results. Consequently, a hybrid solution involving Python and Excel was implemented. More precisely, the tokens from DATAvoc, along with their frequencies, were processed using an Excel file (Figure 2). From now on, that file will be referred to as the “Comparison Spreadsheet”¹. The results obtained from CODE4 for both WAWvoc and WSETvoc were also incorporated into the spreadsheet. Subsequently, a manual review of the spreadsheet was conducted to ensure consistent designation to a vocabulary for all variations of the same word. The procedure is illustrated in Figure 3.

TOKEN	FREQUENCY	WAW	final WAW	WSET	final WSET	Comparison
abrasive	96	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
acacia	254	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
acai	22	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
acetic	7	YES	YES	NO	NO	WAW
acetone	2	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
acid	624	YES	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET
acidic	462	NO	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET
acidity	24597	NO	YES	YES	YES	WAW/WSET
acids	243	NO	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET
afterburn	1	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL

WAW	final WAW	WSET	final WSET	WAW/WSET	NULL
0	0	0	0	0	96
0	0	0	0	0	254
0	0	0	0	0	22
7	7	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	2
624	624	0	624	624	0
0	462	0	462	462	0
0	24597	24597	24597	24597	0
0	243	0	243	243	0
0	0	0	0	0	1

Figure 2. Sample of the Comparison Spreadsheet

¹ The Comparison Spreadsheet is available at <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1nvjuATYk8eXEF40aXzymIH11jS0d6P87/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=104493436601510445237&rtfpof=true&sd=true>

Figure 3. Workflow for RQ 1

3.3.2 RQ 2:

Do the reviewers display consistent linguistic patterns, or the results of RQ1 could be influenced by the idiolect of certain reviewers?

To answer this question, it was necessary to observe the behavioural patterns of each individual reviewer. For this purpose, nineteen sub-corpora were created, representing each of the reviewers from the original dataset. To ensure balance and representativeness, a random sample of 145 reviews was taken from each of the nineteen reviewers' sub-corpus.

Each sample was subjected to pre-processing, and the frequencies of the tokens were counted using CODE 5-19 (Appendix 6). The output consisted of nineteen

files containing the tokens and their occurrences. Subsequently, CODE 7-19 was utilised to filter out any tokens not found in DATAvoc. In this manner the NULLs for each reviewer were identified and their frequencies counted. The resulting data was then incorporated into the comparison spreadsheet (Appendix 6). Finally, the spreadsheet utilised conditional formulas to compare the data and generate the following information for each reviewer:

- The number of occurrences of WAWvoc words in their reviews along with the percentage of the grand total represented by these occurrences.
- The number of occurrences of WSETvoc words in their reviews along with percentage of the grand total represented by these occurrences.
- The number of occurrences of tokens that overlap between the standardised vocabularies (WAW/WSET) along with the corresponding percentage of the grand total represented by these occurrences.
- The number of occurrences of tokens that do not appear in either of the standardised vocabularies (NULL), along with the corresponding percentage of the grand total represented by these occurrences.

In order to identify any outliers, again using Excel, the mean value of each vocabulary was computed, followed by the calculation of the corresponding standard deviation using the STDEV.S premade formula. The standard deviation serves as a measure of the extent to which values deviate from the average value (the mean), indicating the degree of dispersion among the values. Then the outliers were identified, employing a threshold of two standard deviations. The procedure is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Workflow for RQ 2

3.3.3 RQ 3:

What are the main terms (NULLs) that reviewers use in addition to the WAW and WSET vocabularies? Does their frequency suggest a need for further expansion or completion of the standard vocabularies?

The NULL tokens, in terms of frequency, constitute 26.31% of the total potential aroma/flavour descriptors, which is a significant proportion. Are they providing meaningful information in addition to the standardised vocabularies? If not, then why do the reviewers use them?

Insights into the underlying motivations for the use of NULLs were sought, and the “why” question addressed, through the use of qualitative methods. The following steps were taken into that direction:

The NULL tokens were examined by classifying them into six categories: a) Taste, Flavour, Aroma, and/or Smell, b) Food and Beverage, c) Fruit and/or Vegetable, d) Texture and/or Consistency, e) Descriptive Terms, and f) Wine-related terms. This categorization was necessary for identifying any potential patterns.

Next, a thorough manual review of the tokens was conducted to ensure consistent designation for all variations of the same term, e.g., morphological, orthographical etc. This labelling resulted in 846 unique terms from the total of 1391 NULL terms. The five terms with the highest frequency were selected for further analysis. This analysis aimed to determine if there is a general tendency to use specific new terms.

Wine reviews frequently provide recommendations regarding wine and food pairing. Consequently, the first step in addressing these queries was to confirm that the NULL terms discovered pertained solely to wine aromas and tastes, rather than to paired food. Secondly to examine why and how those descriptors were used by the reviewers. Corpus Linguistics methods, quantitative and qualitative, were employed to achieve this and to delve further into the findings. Specifically, the Concordances and Collocations of the top five NULL terms were analysed using Sketch Engine (Lexical Computing CZ s.r.o.). A deeper examination of the top five terms in frequency (the roots “juic-”, “dark”, “crisp”, “firm”, “structur-” was performed, examining frequency and typicality. Frequency and typicality are metrics used in text analysis to evaluate collocations - word combinations that co-occur more frequently than by chance (Gablasova et al., 2017). Frequency refers to the occurrence rate of word combinations in texts, with those appearing often being predictable and less informative, known as weak collocations. Typicality refers to less predictable but meaningful word combinations, termed strong collocations. These provide more insight into the unique characteristics and nuances of the text. Tools like Sketch Engine prioritize typicality over frequency in text analysis, using an algorithm to calculate a collocation score and identify strong collocations. This aids in better understanding and interpreting the text (Most frequent or most typical collocations?, n.d.). The strength of collocation is expressed by the logDice score, a statistic measure for identifying co-occurrence. The scale of logDice ranges from -14 to +14, where -14 indicates no association, and +14 indicates a very strong association (Rychlý, 2008). Both frequency and logDice score can provide useful insights, but they highlight different aspects of the data. Both measures were used, to better understand how the emerging terms are being used by the reviewers in the dataset. Then, the results from that analysis were evaluated in conjunction with various glossaries and articles explaining wine terms. The procedure is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Workflow for RQ 3

4 Results and Discussion

Wine discourse strives to capture the intricacies of sensory experiences, distinguishing it from conventional modes of communication, as a distinct genre. The research conducted to date has demonstrated the inherent limitations of English as well as most other languages in the representation of olfactory and gustatory stimuli, which present significant obstacles to effectively communicating sensory experiences. The nuanced nature of those particular sensory impressions, results in a certain level of uncertainty within wine discourse, that makes them difficult to be effectively conveyed. This uncertainty has sparked an ongoing scholarly discussion regarding the informative nature of wine reviews, highlighting the need for additional research. As a response to this challenge, considerable efforts have been devoted to the development of standardised vocabularies which aimed at enhancing the precision and clarity of wine descriptions and facilitate their meaning and accuracy. While significant research has been conducted on the expressive means language uses to communicate the sensory experiences of wine, it appears that the available research does not extensively cover the actual impact of standardised vocabularies, indicating a potential research gap that warrants further study. In light of these considerations, the purpose of this study is to observe the adherence of professional wine reviewers to two widely recognised standardised vocabularies, namely WAW and WSET. Moreover, it attempts to identify linguistic patterns employed by reviewers and assess the presence of additional terms that extend beyond the two established frameworks under examination. The subsequent sections of this chapter will present and explain the findings derived from the dataset and methodology previously described, for each one of the three research questions.

4.1 RQ 1:

Do the wine reviews adhere to a standardised set of terms from the WAW and WSET vocabularies? If wine reviews do follow a standardised set of terms, which vocabulary, WAW or WSET, is more frequently used? Are there also other terms incorporated in wine reviews, in addition to the standardised terms?

The results from the procedure described in the Methodology chapter (see Table 1) revealed that a significant proportion of the terms used in the reviews, specifically 65.79%, demonstrated adherence to the WSET vocabulary. WSET is widely regarded as the leading authority in wine education and certification. Their curriculum and study materials are frequently updated to reflect the most recent industry practices and developments. This includes revising their lexicon to incorporate new terms, as well as refining or discarding existing ones. For the purpose of this study, the WSET lexicon utilised corresponds to the most recent version from 2022. The practice of regularly updating the lexicon could account for the prevalence of WSET vocabulary among the reviewers.

In contrast, the terms adhering to WAW, which had last undergone modifications in 1987, accounted for a lesser percentage, specifically 47.06%. This stark disparity in adherence rates suggests that the influence of WSET and its updated materials plays a more significant role in shaping the language and content of the reviews compared

to the outdated WAW framework. However, it is important to note that 39.16% of the terms used in the reviews are common between WAW and WSET, indicating a significant overlap or shared vocabulary between the two frameworks.

	Reviews	% of Reviews
TOTAL WAW	342,410	47.06%
TOTAL WSET	478,656	65.79%
TOTAL WAW/WSET	284,938	39.16%
NULL	191,465	26.31%
GRAND TOTAL	727,593	100.00%

Table 1. Adherence of reviews to standardised vocabularies

WAW in its time was a groundbreaking tool primarily aiming to facilitate effective communication among members of the wine industry and consumers alike. It provided a standardised language with a hierarchical classification of aroma and flavour descriptors, making it easier for the taster to recognise them and progress from general to specific characteristics. Along with the selection and classification of the descriptors went a list of chemicals to serve as reference standards. Overall, it was a highly significant effort to make the wine terminology as accurate and representative as possible. Nevertheless, as it is widely recognised, language undergoes changes over time as a result of diverse factors, encompassing cultural, social, and technological influences, among others. Similarly, wine discourse undergoes changes that can be due to:

- Cultural shifts and trends and consumer preferences. For example, in recent years terms like “natural wine” and “orange wine” have gained popularity. Natural wine refers to wine made from unaltered fermented grape juice, without any additional substances or modifications (Woolf, 2017). On the other hand, orange wine is a type of white wine where the grapes are left to ferment in contact with their skins (Wilson, 2020), a process typically used for red wines.
- Technological advancements in winemaking technology. For example, specialised yeasts or temperature-controlled fermentation (Gardner et al., 2023) may require new terms.
- Globalisation and Inclusivity. In our days, the production as well as the consumption of wine is not limited in the western world. According to the World Population Review (2023), in year 2023, China ranks ninth in world wine production (with 1,163,600 litres/year) and South Africa eighth (with 1,080,100 litres/year). China also ranks sixth in overall wine consuming. This global opening of wine creates the need for rethinking about the current standardised vocabularies which are using Euro-centric descriptors that do not cover the sensory knowledge and memory of people from other parts of the world. To quote Lambert (2023), “The term gooseberry, for example, is confusing to most South Africans. The local version isn’t the tart, green English one commonly used as a Sauvignon Blanc descriptor; the Cape gooseberry is orange, with sweet flesh”. Hence, there is currently a wide discussion in the wine industry about “decolonising” wine descriptors

and adjusting them to include a broader demographic (Caputo, 2023; Hill, 2022).

Another characteristic of WAW is the deliberate omission of any descriptors with a hedonic or value-judgment connotations (e.g., well-rounded, good/bad, (un)balanced, rich, vinous, young/old, etc). This exclusion was considered necessary due to the inherent subjectivity of such descriptors, making them difficult to define or standardise. WSET on the other hand, includes the conclusions of the tasting, assessing the quality as poor, acceptable, good, very good, outstanding, and the suitability for bottle ageing.

In conclusion, concerning RQ 1, it can be inferred that wine reviews predominantly adhere to standardised terms. The analysis of the dataset, as illustrated in Figures 6 and 7, indicates that WSET vocabulary is used more frequently than WAW. However, an intriguing finding has emerged revealing that a significant proportion of other terms is incorporated in wine reviews in addition to the standardised ones. Notably, it was found that 26.32% of the terms used in the dataset do not align with either of the two established frameworks (NULLs).

Figure 6. Volume of each set of descriptors vs total

Figure 7. Percentage of Vocabulary Appearance

It is worth highlighting that WSET, in their own account, explicitly acknowledge that their wine lexicon is not “an exhaustive list, but it’s a great starting point” (How to keep things fun when practising wine tasting, 2023). As mentioned in earlier chapters, the use of standardised vocabularies in wine reviews is of great importance

as far as clarity and effective communication of wine experiences is concerned. Hence, when terms are used outside regulated frameworks, in this case a proportion of 26.31%, two possibilities arise: either these terms convey the same meaning, potentially causing confusion and hindering effective communication, or they carry a different meaning, requiring further examination of their significance and relevance. Before proceeding with such an analysis, it is necessary to ascertain whether the NULL values exhibit a relatively uniform distribution throughout the dataset or if they are associated with specific reviewers.

4.2 RQ 2:

Do the reviewers display consistent linguistic patterns, or the results of RQ1 could be influenced by the idiolect of certain reviewers?

As mentioned in the Literature Review chapter, the reviewer's memory and knowledge can shape their sensory perception of the wine tasted. The same cognitive functions affect the words they use to describe it. Brochet and Dubourdieu (2001) argue that wine experts use individual discourse strategies, which are distinct and not commonly shared with colleagues, therefore display an idiolect which makes mutual comprehension difficult. However, the results obtained in the present research (see Table 2 and Figure 8) did not fully support that.

More precisely, the analysis of the reviewers' linguistic patterns and their usage of the WAW vocabulary revealed that the range of WAW vocabulary usage spans from 36.95% to 49.69% of their total vocabulary. The mean percentage of WAW vocabulary usage among the reviewers was calculated to be 43.42%, with a standard deviation of 3.84. To identify any outliers, a threshold was set using two standard deviations. The upper bound for WAW vocabulary usage is calculated as the mean (43.42%) plus two standard deviations (3.84×2), resulting in an upper bound of 51.09%. Similarly, the lower bound is calculated as the mean minus two standard deviations, resulting in a lower bound of 35.75%. This information indicates that the majority of reviewers fall within the range of approximately 35.75% to 51.09% of WAW vocabulary usage. Based on this criterion, it was determined that no outliers were detected among the reviewers in terms of their WAW vocabulary usage. Overall, these findings suggest that reviewers generally exhibit consistent usage patterns for the WAW vocabulary, with the majority falling within the range defined by the mean and standard deviation.

Moving on to the WSET vocabulary, the analysis of reviewers' linguistic patterns revealed that their usage of the WSET vocabulary spans a range of 60.95% to 73.45% of their total vocabulary. The mean percentage of WSET vocabulary usage among the reviewers was calculated to be 68.17%, with a standard deviation of 3.61. This indicates that the majority of reviewers fall within the range of approximately 60.95% to 75.45% of WSET vocabulary usage. Again, the reviewers' usage of the WSET vocabulary is consistent, with most of the reviewers falling within the range defined by the mean and standard deviation.

Finally, on the NULL vocabulary, the analysis (see Fig. 5) reveals that reviewers' usage of the NULL vocabulary ranges from 19.89% to 32.64% of their total vocabulary. The mean percentage of NULL vocabulary usage among the reviewers is calculated to be 25.15%, with a standard deviation of 3.48. This indicates that the majority of reviewers falls within the range of approximately 18.20% to 32.10% of NULL vocabulary usage.

REVIEWER	WAW	WAW %	WSET	WSET %	NULL	NULL %
N1 - Peartree	729	41.02%	1224	68.88%	424	23.87%
N2 - Iijima	644	39.75%	1064	65.68%	433	26.73%
N3 - Kriebiehl	674	36.95%	1208	66.23%	427	23.41%
N4 - Dykes	797	40.54%	1416	72.02%	391	19.89%
N5 - Pickard	766	45.33%	1195	70.71%	376	22.25%
N6 - Adams	1082	42.60%	1765	69.49%	619	24.37%
N7 - Jenssen	782	45.76%	1158	67.76%	432	25.28%
N8 - Gordon	557	42.75%	957	73.45%	289	22.21%
N9 - Czerwinski	503	37.68%	924	69.21%	320	23.97%
N10 - O'Keefe	816	41.27%	1274	64.44%	560	28.33%
N11 - Buzzeo	884	46.23%	1331	69.61%	457	23.90%
N12 - Kettmann	800	37.83%	1289	60.95%	690	32.62%
N13 - Schachner	892	48.45%	1201	65.24%	437	23.74%
N14 - De Simone	949	46.11%	1493	72.55%	450	21.87%
N15 - Gregutt	576	44.10%	798	61.10%	426	32.64%
N16 - Voss	481	45.12%	719	67.45%	312	29.27%
N17 - Sullivan	641	49.69%	943	73.10%	287	22.25%
N18 - Kostrzewa	791	49.04%	1119	69.37%	400	24.80%
N19 - Boone	613	44.68%	933	68.00%	363	26.46%

Table 2. RQ 2 Results

It is noteworthy that during the analysis, two outliers were identified among the reviewers in terms of their NULL vocabulary usage. Reviewer N15 – Gregutt exhibits the highest NULL usage at 32.70% (7.54 above the average), while reviewer N12 – Kettmann demonstrates usage at 32.62% (7.46 above the average). These findings indicate that, generally, reviewers display a moderate usage of the NULL vocabulary, with the majority falling within the range defined by the mean and standard deviation.

In general, the analysis suggests that reviewers typically display consistent patterns for the WAW vocabulary. The occurrence of the same outlier in two out of the three vocabularies indicates a persistent inclination on the part of reviewer N15-Gregutt to employ distinctive vocabulary that deviates from the average across different linguistic dimensions. This coherence in vocabulary choice could be attributed to various factors, such as their personal writing style, language preferences, or subject expertise. It is important to note that reviewer N15-Gregutt's usage of both the WSET and NULL vocabularies falls outside the typical range observed among the other reviewers. Reviewer N12-Kettmann appears as an outlier in the NULL vocabulary and touching the upper bound of the WSET vocabulary. The deviation from the norm, observed in the usage of both the WSET and NULL vocabularies by the presence of outliers, may reflect the reviewers' individual linguistic preferences or idiolects, potentially influencing the results obtained in RQ1, which focused on

these vocabularies. These results reveal only two out of nineteen reviewers deviated from the norm, accounting for 10.5% of the total. While further statistical analysis could have provided additional insights into the nature and implications of the reviewers' idiolects, it was decided that, for the scope of this study, considering 79.5% as the "norm" would suffice. Consequently, the study proceeded to address RQ3. Overall, these findings indicate that reviewers generally exhibit a moderate usage of the NULL vocabulary, with the majority falling within the range defined by the mean and standard deviation. The aim of this study is to gain a deeper understanding of the NULLs and how they might influence the communication and interpretation of wine reviews. To achieve this objective, a qualitative approach will be employed, which is believed to provide valuable insights and contribute to a richer understanding of RQ3.

Figure 8. WAW, WSET, and NULL Outliers

4.3 RQ 3:

What are the main terms that reviewers use in addition to the WAW and WSET vocabularies (referred to as "NULL" hereafter)? Does their frequency suggest a need for further expansion or completion of the standard vocabularies?

The frequency of terms classified as "NULLs" within the DATAvoc vocabulary, as revealed by the findings from RQ 1, accounts for 26.31% of all terms. However, they constitute a much larger proportion (71.37%) in terms of tokens. This suggests that "NULLs" are relatively common occurrences but appear less frequently as

distinct values compared to other “DATAvoc terms”. In other words, the reviewers seem to be using a wide range of different “NULL terms”. This trend becomes even more pronounced (79.41%) when the tokens are grouped together following their base word or root concept, which are referred to here as “Net Null Terms”. These findings are illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9. NULLs

4.3.1 Categorisation of the NULL Terms.

To examine the characteristics of the NULLs and facilitate the detection of any patterns, they were classified into six categories: a) Taste, Flavour, Aroma, and/or Smell, b) Food and Beverage, c) Fruit and/or Vegetable, d) Texture and/or Consistency, e) Descriptive Terms, and f) Wine. Additionally, a thorough manual review of the terms was conducted, taking into account morphological and orthographical variations, to ensure consistent designation for all variations of the same term. As a result, the tokens were grouped together based on their base word or root concept (Net Null Terms).

The categorisation of the NULLs into six groups produced the results presented in Table 3. The reviewers utilise a significant portion of non-standardised terms (38.29%) to communicate their sensory impressions of Taste/Flavour/Aroma/Smell. Moreover, they exhibit a remarkable diversity in their expression, employing a wide variety of terms (37.89%) to convey these impressions. Notably, their creativity becomes evident when making associations with food and beverages. In this context, there are 28.76% NULL tokens, yet their frequency accounts for only 7.64%.

DESCRIPTIVE TERMS				
Tokens	Total NULL Tokens	Total DATAvoc Tokens	DTs vs Total NULLs	DT Tokens vs DATAvoc
172	1,391	1,946	12.37%	8.84%
Net Terms	Total Net Nulls	Total Net DATAvoc	Net DTs vs Net NULLs	Net DTs vs Net DATAvoc
59	833	1,049	7.08%	5.62%
Frequency	Total NULL Freq	Total DATAvoc Freq	DT Freq vs Total NULLs	DT Freq vs DATAvoc
56,578	191,465	727,593	29.55%	7.78%
FOOD AND BEVERAGE-RELATED TERMS				
Tokens	Total NULL Tokens	Total DATAvoc Tokens	DTs vs Total NULLs	DT Tokens vs DATAvoc
400	1,391	1,946	28.76%	20.55%
Net Terms	Total Net Nulls	Total Net DATAvoc	Net DTs vs Net NULLs	Net DTs vs Net DATAvoc
295	833	1,049	35.41%	28.12%
Frequency	Total NULL Freq	Total DATAvoc Freq	DT Freq vs Total NULLs	DT Freq vs DATAvoc
14,636	191,465	727,637	7.64%	2.01%
FRUIT/VEGETABLE				
Tokens	Total NULL Tokens	Total DATAvoc Tokens	DTs vs Total NULLs	DT Tokens vs DATAvoc
132	1,391	1,946	9.49%	6.78%
Net Terms	Total Net Nulls	Total Net DATAvoc	Net DTs vs Net NULLs	Net DTs vs Net DATAvoc
93	833	1,049	11.16%	8.87%
Frequency	Total NULL Freq	Total DATAvoc Freq	DT Freq vs Total NULLs	DT Freq vs DATAvoc
11,220	191,465	727,593	5.86%	1.54%
TASTE/FLAVOUR/AROMA/SMELL				
Tokens	Total NULL Tokens	Total DATAvoc Tokens	DTs vs Total NULLs	DT Tokens vs DATAvoc
527	1,391	1,946	37.89%	27.08%
Net Terms	Total Net Nulls	Total Net DATAvoc	Net DTs vs Net NULLs	Net DTs vs Net DATAvoc
317	833	1,049	38.06%	30.22%
Frequency	Total NULL Freq	Total DATAvoc Freq	DT Freq vs Total NULLs	DT Freq vs DATAvoc
73,303	191,465	727,593	38.29%	10.07%
TEXTURE/ CONSISTENCY				
Tokens	Total NULL Tokens	Total DATAvoc Tokens	DTs vs Total NULLs	DT Tokens vs DATAvoc
63	1,391	1,946	4.53%	3.24%
Net Terms	Total Net Nulls	Total Net DATAvoc	Net DTs vs Net NULLs	Net DTs vs Net DATAvoc
24	833	1,049	2.88%	2.29%
Frequency	Total NULL Freq	Total DATAvoc Freq	DT Freq vs Total NULLs	DT Freq vs DATAvoc
10,785	191,465	727,593	5.63%	1.48%
WINE-RELATED TERMS				
Tokens	Total NULL Tokens	Total DATAvoc Tokens	DTs vs Total NULLs	DT Tokens vs DATAvoc
97	1,391	1,946	6.97%	4.98%
Net Terms	Total Net Nulls	Total Net DATAvoc	Net DTs vs Net NULLs	Net DTs vs Net DATAvoc
45	833	1,049	5.40%	4.29%
Frequency	Total NULL Freq	Total DATAvoc Freq	DT Freq vs Total NULLs	DT Freq vs DATAvoc
24,943	191,465	727,593	13.03%	3.43%

Table 3. Categorisation of the NULLs

On the contrary, when it comes to descriptive terms, they use a more limited range (12.37%), but with a higher frequency (29.55%). Additionally, they demonstrate greater consistency when using wine-related terms, with tokens comprising 6.97% and their frequency at 13.03%. The use of terms expressing fruit or vegetable association, as well as those related to the texture and/or consistency of wine, appears to be relatively homogeneous, as they do not display significant contrast.

The terms with the highest frequency in each category were analysed in relation to their proportion within the entire dataset. This analysis aimed to determine if there is

a general tendency to use specific new terms. In Table 4, the terms with a frequency of appearance higher than 1% compared to the total dataset are highlighted in bold.

DESCRIPTIVE TERMS			FOOD AND BEVERAGE-RELATED TERMS		
TERM	FREQUENCY	% OF NULLS	TERM	FREQUENCY	% OF NULLS
juice	8,851	4.6228%	cola	1,271	0.6638%
dark	7,867	4.1088%	game	1,096	0.5724%
crisp	6,812	3.5578%	beef	613	0.3202%
firm	6,284	3.2821%	mousse	551	0.2878%
complex	3,906	2.0401%	pie	490	0.2559%
young	3,205	1.6739%	nut	472	0.2465%
delicious	2,378	1.2420%	crust	437	0.2282%
clean	2,231	1.1652%	compote	412	0.2152%
old	1,810	0.9453%	punch	399	0.2084%
delicate	1,554	0.8116%	milk	394	0.2058%

FRUIT / VEGETABLE			TASTE / FLAVOUR / AROMA / SMELL		
TERM	FREQUENCY	% OF NULLS	TERM	FREQUENCY	% OF NULLS
tangerine	1,569	0.8195%	mineral	5,691	2.9723%
pomegranate	1,147	0.5991%	savor	5,159	2.6945%
blue	1,140	0.5954%	zest	4,515	2.3581%
boysenberry	860	0.4492%	tang	3,896	2.0348%
rhubarb	493	0.2575%	flower	3,842	2.0066%
bramable	473	0.2470%	tart	2,900	1.5146%
honeydew	458	0.2392%	peel	2,617	1.3668%
guava	423	0.2209%	bitter	2,339	1.2216%
mulberry	406	0.2120%	salt	1,914	0.9997%
watermelon	401	0.2094%	sage	1,572	0.8210%

TEXTURE / CONSISTENCY			WINE-RELATED TERMS		
TERM	FREQUENCY	% OF NULLS	TERM	FREQUENCY	% OF NULLS
dense	4,180	2.1832%	structure	5,969	3.1175%
flesh	1,678	0.8764%	barrel	3,229	1.6865%
pith	1,282	0.6696%	edge	2,879	1.5037%
chew	810	0.4231%	vine	1,842	0.9621%
chunk	464	0.2423%	skin	1,623	0.8477%
crunch	448	0.2340%	aftertaste	1,456	0.7605%
gravel	396	0.2068%	mouth	1,209	0.6314%
oil	385	0.2011%	length	1,161	0.6064%
viscous	349	0.1823%	midpalate	1,108	0.5787%
clay	235	0.1227%	graphite	953	0.4977%

Table 4. Terms with a % >1 (highlighted in bold) vs Grand Total, by Category.

The analysis produced in total twenty terms, most of which fall into either the Descriptive Terms category or the Taste, Flavour, Aroma, and Smell category, and a few in the Wine-Related and Texture/Consistency categories, as illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10. NULL terms with a % >1

4.3.2 Analysis of the Emerged Terms

A deeper examination of the top five terms in frequency (the roots “juic-”, “dark”, “crisp”, “firm”, “structur-” was performed using Sketch Engine. Frequency and typicality are metrics used in text analysis to evaluate collocations - word combinations that co-occur more frequently than by chance (Gablasova et al., 2017). Frequency refers to the occurrence rate of word combinations in texts, with those appearing often being predictable and less informative, known as weak collocations. Typicality refers to less predictable but meaningful word combinations, termed strong collocations. These provide more insight into the unique characteristics and nuances of the text. Tools like Sketch Engine prioritize typicality over frequency in text analysis, using an algorithm to calculate a collocation score and identify strong collocations. This aids in better understanding and interpreting the text (Most frequent or most typical collocations?, n.d.). The strength of collocation is expressed by the logDice score, a statistic measure for identifying co-occurrence. The scale of logDice ranges from -14 to +14, where -14 indicates no association, and +14 indicates a very strong association (Rychlý, 2008). Both frequency and logDice score can provide useful insights, but they highlight different aspects of the data. To better understand how the emerging terms are being used by the reviewers in the dataset, both measures were used. Then, the results from that analysis were evaluated in conjunction with various glossaries and articles explaining wine terms.

4.3.2.1 The Root “juic-”

The terms associated with the root *juic-* make up 4.62% of the NULL vocabulary. The most frequent forms in the dataset are “juicy”, “juice”, and “juiciness” (see Table 5). Given the high frequency of “juicy” relative to other forms of the root, focus was placed on this term.

ROOT: juic-			
Word	Frequency	Word	Frequency
juicy	8,576	juiciest	9
juice	722	juices	7
juiciness	397	juiced	6
juicier	33	juicness	1
juicily	10		

Table 5. Terms from the root “juic-”

In a few instances, the term “juicy” is used to describe the fruit whose notes are detected in the wine tasting (see Figure 11). In most cases, though it characterises the wine itself. The latter usage will be examined here.

ers an intricate play between texture and acidity, **juicy fruit** and taut, sandy tannins, hintir
 s>"Big and rich, this generous wine has spice, **juicy** black **fruits** and fine tannins.</s><
 'This structured wine has fine tannins as well as **juicy** red **fruits** .</s><s>Acidity and spic
 he dense texture that has now softened into the **juicy** blackberry **fruits** .</s><s>The bler
 This rich wine from a 240-acre vineyard is full of **juicy** black **fruits** and ripe tannins.</s><

Figure 11. Random sample of concordances of “juicy” as a fruit descriptor

Frequency and logDice scores provide us with two different types of information when we look at the nouns modified by juicy: frequency reveals how frequently a specific noun is modified by “juicy”, while logDice scores demonstrate how strongly a noun is associated with “juicy” in relation to the frequency of that noun overall in the dataset. As illustrated on Figure 12, the top two nouns most frequently modified by “juicy” are “fruit” and “cherry”. However, looking at the logDice scores, “cherry” has a higher score (9.9) than fruit (9.4), even though “fruit” has a higher frequency. This suggests that while “juicy” is used more often to describe “fruit”, the association between “juicy” and “cherry” is stronger. Moving further down the list, “juicy” is also often used to describe “acidity”, “palate”, and “wine”, among others. The fact that “juicy” is frequently used with “acidity” and has a high logDice score (9.7) could indicate that a “juicy” wine is often one with pronounced or noticeable acidity. Interestingly, the term “tannin” appears at the bottom of the list with a relatively low logDice score of 2.6, suggesting that “juicy” is rarely used to describe tannins.

Examining the subjects of *be* “juicy”, “palate” has both the highest frequency (131) and a very high logDice score (9.8), indicating that the palate of the wine is frequently and distinctively described as being “juicy” (see Figure 13). On the other hand, “wine” emerges as the second most common subject connected with “juicy” (103 times), but with a slightly reduced logDice score (8.7). This indicates a common tendency to describe wine in general as “juicy”, although this usage is not as marked as when referring specifically to the palate’s juiciness.

nouns modified by "juicy"			subjects of "be juicy"		
fruit	939	9.4 ...	palate	131	9.8 ...
cherry	651	9.9 ...	wine	103	8.7 ...
acidity	623	9.7 ...	flavor	47	9.0 ...
palate	509	9.6 ...	finish	19	7.9 ...
wine	392	8.4 ...	fruit	15	8.6 ...
flavor	386	7.8 ...	red	9	9.1 ...
pear	165	9.0 ...	aftertaste	6	8.7 ...
character	152	8.7 ...			
peach	115	8.5 ...			
plum	103	8.1 ...			
aftertaste	101	8.7 ...			
dole	96	8.7 ...			

Figure 12. Collocates of “juicy”

Overall, these results suggest that the term “juicy” is frequently used to refer to the overall experience of wine, particularly in the palate, and denotes a wine with pronounced, fruit-forward flavours, often accompanied by noticeable acidity (see Figure 14). These results were then cross verified using various oenology glossaries and articles, to ensure a comprehensive understanding and interpretation of the data within the broader context of wine studies.

The term “*palate*” in oenology denotes the sensory impression of a wine’s flavour or taste, often discussed in relation to distinct zones within the oral cavity. As the wine traverses through the mouth, it sequentially interacts with the anterior palate, the medial palate, and ultimately the posterior palate. Each region discerns distinct taste modalities, encompassing sweetness, sourness, and bitterness (Glossary, n.d.).

Malvasia Nera.	The medium-bodied palate is juicy	in feel, driven by watermelon and citrus
nose.	Light to medium in weight, the palate is juicy	in tree fruit tones yet balanced by a
citrus and clove.	A medium-bodied palate is juicy	in red and black berry flavors, flecked
with herbs and tobacco.	The entry to the palate is juicy	and enticing in a fresh red berry flavor
on the nose.	The medium-bodied palate is juicy	in sour red cherry, with tangy acidity

Figure 13. Random sample of concordances of “palate”, in the dataset

“Aftertaste” or “Finish” is the impression left on the palate after the wine is tasted and has been removed from the mouth. It is the most important factor in evaluating the quality of a wine (Glossary, n.d.). When the word “juicy” is collocated with “aftertaste”, it refers to a flavourful aftertaste that reminds one of fresh juice.

In summary, the results of the research appear to be in accordance with the information derived from glossaries and informative articles. The term “juicy” is predominantly employed to depict the sensory impressions experienced on the

palate, especially those related to acidity. This is because acidity incites salivation, thereby imparting a “juicy” characteristic to the wine (Hartley, 2011).

Figure 14. Collocations of “juicy”.

Note: The illustration is depicting the collocations of “juicy” with the nouns it modifies as well as the subjects of “be juicy”. In this visualisation Typicality is reflected by the distance from the centre, and Frequency by the circle size.

It's important to highlight at this juncture that according to López-Arroyo and Roberts' (2015) study, the term 'juicy', when used in the context of wine reviews, serves as a descriptor with a broad application. This characterisation stems from their method of classifying wine descriptors, which involves five distinct “moves”, each comprising multiple “steps”, as illustrated in Figure 15.

Table 2. Moves and steps for wine tasting notes.

Introductory remarks (IR)
Appearance (AP)
Colour hue and depth
Clarity
Viscosity
Effervescence
Aroma (AR)
Fragrance
Intensity
Development
Taste (TA)
Flavors
Finish
Astringency
Mouthfeel
Body
Balance
Concluding remarks (CR)

Figure 15. The López-Arroyo and Roberts (2015) classification.

López-Arroyo and Roberts create a distinction between olfaction and gustation. However, a prevailing consensus amongst researchers in the behavioural and brain sciences maintains that taste and odour are components of flavour (Gotow & Kobayakawa, 2022). In wine tasting, the brain simultaneously takes input from those two different sensory modalities (in fact not only two, as tactility and vision are also involved) and forms a holistic perception of the experience. Very often,

there is also congruency between the two modalities, for example a ripe Cantaloupe melon can taste and smell sweet. Drawing from those insights, this paper argues that that the term “juicy” serves a particular purpose in wine reviews.

4.3.2.2 The Root *dark*

The terms affiliated with the root “dark” constitute 4.11% of the NULL vocabulary. The most prevalent forms identified in the dataset are “dark” and “darker” (see Table 6). Emphasis was placed on “dark” due to its significantly higher frequency compared to other forms originating from the same root.

ROOT: dark-			
Word	Frequency	Word	Frequency
dark	7998	darkens	5
darker	229	darken	4
darkly	42	darkish	3
darkness	28	darkening	1
darkest	7	darkchocolaty	1
darkened	5		

Table 6. Terms from the root “dark-”

nouns modified by "dark"				subjects of "be dark"			
fruit	1,203	9.7	...	wine	43	7.5	...
berry	939	10.9	...	aroma	10	7.2	...
chocolate	784	11.4	...	color	8	10.6	...
flavor	687	8.6	...	taste	5	8.7	...
cherry	548	9.6	...	flavor	5	5.9	...
spice	452	10.0	...	palate	5	5.1	...
aroma	365	8.3	...				
plum	239	9.2	...				
tannin	227	8.1	...				
color	193	9.5	...				
wine	86	6.2	...				
note	83	6.8	...				

Figure 16. Collocates of “dark”

The examination of collocations showed that “dark” appears to be more commonly used as an attribute than as the predicate nominative of a subject, as illustrated in Figure 16. The top nouns most frequently modified by “dark” are “fruit”, “berry”, and “chocolate”. Similarly, the top frequent subjects of be “dark” are “wine”, “aroma”, and “color”.

In a few cases (46 as modifier of a noun and 43 as the predicate nominative of a subject, to be precise), “dark” is describing *wine* and therefore refers to its colour, which falls out of the scope of this study. An example is provided in figure 17. On the other hand, the three predominant nouns modified by “dark” display high logDice scores, particularly “chocolate”, with 11.4, “berry” with 10.9, and “fruit”, with 9. “Dark” usually defines the colour of object that has the particular flavour or aroma and in most cases it is food. For example, “chocolate”, “cherry”, “plum”, etc. Overall, the descriptor “dark” assumes considerable significance in the wine reviews (see Figure 18). Its application is multifaceted, offering a remarkable degree of specificity when collocated with nouns. For instance, “dark fruit” refers to dark-skinned fruit like blackberries, black cherry, blackcurrant, etc. (Stern, 2017). Also, “dark chocolate” implies a flavour profile distinct from that of “milk chocolate”, and “dark plums” suggest a heightened aromatic intensity compared to their lighter. Consequently, although “dark” may appear generic in isolation, it conveys nuanced sensory impressions in context.

ahead of it. </s><s>The color is dark and intense right to the rim, while aromas ble
tizing.</s><s>The color is quite dark , and the black cherry, blackberry and raspbe
late flavors.</s><s>The color is dark and deep, tannins are very firm, and the mou
thfeel.</s><s>The color is quite dark , the aromas are smoky and peppery and the
e.</s><s>The color is about as dark as it gets, the mouthfeel is massive and yet th
ill turns.</s><s>The color is not darker than water, and the aromas are extremely juik
e released.</s><s>The color is dark and vibrant, and it opens with orange peel, be
ked and because the color was dark .</s><s>This strongly wood aged bottling rec

Figure 17. A random example of “color” concordances

Figure 18. Collocations of “dark”.

Note: The illustration is depicting the collocations of “dark” with the nouns it modifies as well as the subjects of “be dark”. Typicality and Frequency are reflected as previously.

Indeed, online oenology literature confirms that kind of specificity is meaningful and informative. Wines that manifest chocolate notes usually derive them from oak in their ageing process, that comes mainly from the barrels. These flavours can vary, ranging from dark chocolate and milk chocolate or cocoa (O'Reilly, n.d.; Dr. Vinny, 2020).

4.3.2.3 The Root *crisp*

The terms linked to the root “crisp” constitute 3.56% of the NULL vocabulary. The forms most frequently derived from this root, as identified in the dataset, are “crisp” as an adjective, “crispness”, and “crisply” (see Table 7). As “crisp” is noted to occur significantly more frequently compared to other variants originating from the same root, the analysis primarily concentrated on this term.

ROOT: crisp-			
Word	Frequency	Word	Frequency
crisp	7221	crispened	13
crispness	390	crispest	12
crisply	265	crispens	1
crisper	103	crisped	1
crispy	13		

Table 7. Terms from the root “crisp-”

nouns modified by "crisp"				subjects of "be crisp"			
acidity	1,063	10.6	...	wine	189	9.6	...
fruit	368	8.1	...	palate	55	8.5	...
wine	366	8.4	...	finish	29	8.5	...
texture	349	9.8	...	flavor	27	8.2	...
apple	276	9.5	...	acidity	13	9.0	...
flavor	267	7.3	...	fruit	13	8.4	...
aftertaste	220	10.2	...	aftertaste	12	9.6	...
edge	187	9.7	...	rosé	7	8.7	...
finish	187	8.6	...	accent	5	8.3	...
palate	139	7.9	...	white	5	8.1	...
character	86	8.1	...	blend	5	8.1	...
aroma	72	6.1	...	aroma	5	6.0	...

Figure 19. Collocates of “crisp”

Going through the nouns modified by “crisp”, the term “acidity” is the most frequent collocate and also has the highest logDice score, 10.6 (see Figures 19 and 20). This indicates a strong association between these terms and suggests that “crisp” is often used to describe a sharp, vibrant acidity in wine.

Figure 20. Collocations of “crisp”.

Note: The illustration is depicting the collocations of “crisp” with the nouns it modifies, as well as the subjects of “be crisp”. Typicality and Frequency are reflected as previously.

In the world of oenology, the descriptor “crisp” is used to describe a white or rosé wine that is acidic and dry, as illustrated in Figure 21). This specific balance of characteristics results in a tart flavour sensation that can be aptly compared to the refreshing zest of freshly-squeezed lemonade (Crispy Wines, 2023; Glossary, n.d.; Hale, 2023; Teeter, 2016). As the term is based on acidity, it is close to “juicy” but defines different qualities. “Juicy” refers to a wine defined by its fruit flavours and mouthwatering quality, while a “crispy” wine is more about its elevated acidity and invigorating, tart qualities. Nevertheless, the two terms can overlap, and a wine could be characterised as both “juicy” and “crispy” if it has high fruit flavours along with high acidity.

Figure 21. Acidity levels in wine (Hale, 2023)

Upon examining the concordances of “crisp”, it becomes obvious that the term can either define the wine itself (see Figure 22) or the fruit associated with the flavour detected in wine (see Figure 23). However, even in the latter case, it implies an acidic taste.

```
<s>This straightforward Trebbiano is crisp , refreshing and driven by bright acidity.</s>
<s>The finish is crisp and clean.</s>
<s>The light bodied palate is crisp and refreshing, with white cherry and mineral sensations that l
<s>The acidity is drawing yet well honed, giving a wine that's refreshing, crisp and begging to be
<s>This is a crisp , refreshing Chardonnay, perfect for simple enjoyment.</s>
```

Figure 22. Random sample of concordances of “crisp” as a descriptor of the wine

```
<s>There's a pleasing roundness to the palate, with a textured, fuzzy feel that carries flavors of crisp apple and lemon u
<s>The clean cut palate is lithe, with crisp green apple and tart quince riding along a streamlined river of acidity.</s>
<s> Crisp apple and pear flavors are a bit lean in concentration, but sunny lemon acidity lingers brightly on the finish.</s
<s>"Cutting crisp tangerine, peach and honeydew melons abound on the nose of this full bodied textured Sauvignon E
<s>"While dense on the palate with bold alcohol and big tannins, crisp black plum and cassis flavors show pristinely on
```

Figure 23. Random sample of concordances of “crisp” as a descriptor of fruit

Overall, “crisp” appears to be a significant term in wine reviews that conveys a particular meaning associated with acidity, and fruity flavours in wine. This descriptor can significantly influence the reader’s perception of the wine, highlighting its refreshing and balanced qualities.

4.3.2.4 The Root “firm-”

The terms associated with the root “firm-” comprise 3.28% of the NULL vocabulary. This root is polysemous: when used as an adjective it means something that is securely or solidly fixed in a place, something that is steady, well-founded, not weak or uncertain. As a noun though it means a company or business (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). Accordingly, “firm’s” and “firma” display were disregarded as their semantic meaning is not relevant to the present study. The most frequently appearing forms in the dataset are “firm”, and “firmly” (see Table 8). Given the high frequency of “firm”, relative to other forms of the root, focus was primarily placed on this term, while special care has been taken to exclude versions of the root that have different meanings.

ROOT: firm-			
Word	Frequency	Word	Frequency
firm	6267	firmed	15
firmly	681	firms	8
firmness	57	firiming	4
firmer	30	firma	2
firm's	18		

Table 8. Terms from the root “firm-”

In this instance, Sketch Engine's automated part-of-speech tagging produced inaccurate outcomes. A very high proportion of the occurrences of the term “firm” were classified as nouns which seemed highly unlikely, so concordances were checked and it was proved that 83% of the occurrences of “firm” were tagged as nouns instead of adjectives. To resolve this problem the tagged dataset was downloaded from Sketch Engine, corrections were made, and then the amended dataset was uploaded again.

nouns modified by "firm"				subjects of "be firm"		
tannin	2,493	11.5	...	tannin	135	11.6 ...
palate	362	9.1	...	wine	108	8.8 ...
structure	349	10.5	...	structure	34	10.9 ...
acidity	294	8.7	...	palate	27	7.5 ...
texture	199	9.0	...	finish	15	7.5 ...
finish	141	8.2	...	texture	13	8.9 ...
wine	133	6.8	...	family	4	8.4 ...
core	81	8.6	...	bit	4	6.5 ...
offer	69	8.4	...			
grip	55	8.3	...			
backbone	32	7.7	...			
character	32	6.6	...			

Figure 24. Collocates of “firm”

Figure 25. Collocations of “firm”.

Note: The illustration is depicting the collocations of “firm” with nouns it modifies as well as the subjects of “be firm”. Typicality and Frequency are reflected as previously.

The strongest collocation of nouns modified by firm, with a logDice score of 11.5, as well as by far the most frequent one, is “tannin”. *Tannins* are polyphenols naturally present in grape ligature (skins, seeds, leaves, and stems) and oak (barrel). They contribute to the bitterness and astringency of wine, enhancing its complexity. Tannins are predominantly found in red wines but can also be detected in some white wines that have been aged in wooden barrels or fermented on skins. Tannins

have more of a texture and feel than a specific flavour and they are often also described as a grippy or structured feel (Tardi, n.d.; Vinepair staff, n.d.; Schiessl, 2016). All these qualities are reflected in the collocations of “firm”, in Figure 25 and a sample of its concordances is illustrated in Figure 26.

<s>There's density to the lush fruit on the medium bodied palate, supported by firm tannins and well balanced acidity.</s>
 <s>There's richness to the fruit on the palate, but it all feels quite fresh and crunchy due to the bright acidity and firm tannins.</s>
 <s>Tart cherry and spice grace the medium bodied palate, held in check by a firm structure.</s>
 <s>There's a silken feel to the palate, with red plum and cherry flavors bolstered by a firm grip of tannins.</s>
 <s>There's a tautness to the overall feel from the tense acidity and firm tannins making it savory and mouthwatering.</s>
 <s>The finish is marked by firm , gripping tannins.</s>
 <s>It feels firm and structured due to good acidity, which supports the surprisingly bright and layered fruit flavors very well.</s>
 <s>A very firm texture shows plenty of acidity and a healthy coating of tannin.</s>
 <s>Good doses of ripe fruit and oaky spices in the aroma and flavor are carried on a firm structure of supportive tannins and fruit acidity.</s>
 <s>Toasted baguette and baking spice nuances complement good, ripe berry and black plum flavors while a firm moderately tannic texture adds good grip.</s>

Figure 26. Random sample of the concordances of “firm”

Going through the online literature, the descriptor “firm” refers to a wine that has noticeable structure or texture. This characteristic can come from the wine's tannins or its acidity. A firm wine has a sensation or feel that tugs on the sides of the mouth or has a grip. It is a descriptor of how the wine feels in the mouth and is neither inherently positive nor negative and it is mainly associated with red wines (Dr.Vinny, 2018). Therefore, the findings align with the literature.

Although the description of a wine as firm is strongly associated with its tannins, it should not be confused with a wine characterised as tannic. In a tannic wine, the tannins are notably aggressive. Not just the quantity, but the management and ripeness of the tannins are equally critical in a wine. It’s expected that all young red wines destined for maturation will contain tannins, but ideally, these should be balanced with the presence of fruit flavours for a more harmonious taste (Glossary, n.d.). Therefore, firm is a descriptor that carries a quite specific meaning.

4.3.2.5 The Root “structure-”

The terms associated with the root “structur-” comprise 3.12% of the NULL vocabulary. The most frequent forms of this root appearing in the dataset are “structure” and “structured” (see Table 9). Since they both occur with high frequencies, the analysis focussed on both these two forms. The form “structure” is manifested either as a noun (5,133 tokens), or as a verb (with a frequency of 2,328 tokens), while the form “structured” only as an adjective (2,078 tokens).

ROOT: structur-			
Word	Frequency	Word	Frequency
structure	5146	structurally	14
structured	4380	structures	2
structural	36	structurd	1
structuring	26		

Table 9. Terms from the root “structur-”

Observing the collocations of “structure” as a noun, the most frequent modifiers of the term are “firm”, and “tannic”, also displaying high logDice scores, indicating that the structure of wine is often described in terms of the level of tannins and firmness. It is also observed that “structure” often appears in conjunction with “fruit”, “acidity”, and “tannin”, which suggests that such qualities are often considered when discussing a wine’s structure (see Figures 27 and 28).

modifiers of "structure"				"structure" and/or ...				possessors of "structure"			
firm	349	10.5	...	fruit	301	9.0	...	wine	51	10.0	...
tannic	314	11.1	...	acidity	265	9.2	...	palate	5	9.9	...
good	138	9.4	...	tannin	256	9.3	...				
tannin	102	9.8	...	flavor	135	7.6	...				
solid	102	9.6	...	texture	100	8.8	...				
light	92	8.7	...	concentration	94	9.6	...				
great	82	8.9	...	balance	74	9.4	...				
rich	68	7.9	...	richness	63	9.0	...				
moderate	64	9.1	...	wine	59	7.6	...				
dense	64	8.7	...	density	55	9.2	...				
powerful	52	8.7	...	elegance	41	8.8	...				
enough	48	8.8	...	weight	41	8.6	...				

Figure 28. Collocates of “structure” as a noun

Figure 27. Collocations of “structure” as a noun.
Note: The illustration is depicting the collocations of “structure” with its modifiers, also “and/or” collocates, as well as with its possessors. Typicality and Frequency are reflected as previously.

As a verb, the root “structure-”is often modified by adverbs that suggest precision, care, and a high degree of skill, like “firmly”, “elegantly”, “well”. This implies that when structure is used as a verb in this corpus, it refers to an action carried out with attention on achieving a specific, finely tuned result. The most frequent objects of “structure” are “wine” and “palate”, with also high logDice scores, 9.9, and 10.3 respectively, suggesting that structure is an action related to the wine and the palate (see Figures 29 and 30).

objects of "structure"				modifiers of "structure"			
wine	550	9.9	...	firmly	301	12.1	...
palate	179	10.3	...	elegantly	182	11.5	...
tannin	65	8.8	...	well	139	9.5	...
offer	25	9.5	...	richly	124	10.6	...
fruit	15	6.1	...	lightly	117	9.7	...
blend	12	7.3	...	finely	60	9.9	...
dole	11	8.4	...	densely	43	9.4	...
flavor	9	4.9	...	beautifully	39	9.0	...
Sauvignon	5	7.1	...	enough	33	9.2	...
Chardonnay	5	7.1	...	tightly	31	8.3	...
mineral	4	6.8	...	moderately	29	8.8	...
estate	4	6.7	...	seriously	26	9.0	...

Figure 29. Collocates of “structure” as a verb

Finally, the adjective “structured” (see Figures 31 and 32) is most frequently modifying words like “wine”, “palate”, also showing high logDice scores, bolstering the previous findings of the objects of “structure” as verb. It is worth noting that “tannin” is the third term in frequency with a logDice of 7.6, indicating a strong association between the two terms. That means that tannin is an important factor affecting the structure of wine.

The form “structured”, when used in conjunction with other descriptors, most frequently collocates with “rich”, “dense”, “firm”, and “elegant”. These collocations also display high logDice scores, with “rich” scoring 9.2, “dense” and “elegant” 10.0 and firm scoring 9.9, indicating that structure is associated with the character and quality of the wine.

Examining the modifiers of “structured”, provided better understanding of how wine can be structured. It becomes clear that a wine can be characterised as “firmly” or “lightly” structured. Additionally terms like “richly”, “well”, “elegantly”, can be applied to describe the qualities of “structure”.

Figure 30. Collocations of “structure” as a verb.

Note: The illustration is depicting the collocations of the verb to “structure” with its objects, with its modifiers, as well as with its subjects. Typicality and Frequency are reflected as previously.

Examining the modifiers of “structured”, provided better understanding of how wine can be structured. It becomes clear that a wine can be characterised as “firmly” or “lightly” structured. Additionally terms like “richly”, “well”, “elegantly”, can be applied to describe the qualities of “structure”.

nouns modified by "structured"			"structured" and/or ...			modifiers of "structured"		
wine	525	8.9 ...	rich	123	9.2 ...	firmly	46	10.7 ...
palate	246	8.8 ...	dense	108	10.0 ...	lightly	25	8.0 ...
tannin	145	7.6 ...	firm	104	9.9 ...	richly	23	9.1 ...
red	50	8.7 ...	elegant	98	10.0 ...	well	21	7.1 ...
offer	26	8.0 ...	ripe	85	7.9 ...	elegantly	18	9.6 ...
character	26	6.9 ...	full	64	8.9 ...	moderately	8	8.4 ...
fruit	25	4.4 ...	savory	41	8.5 ...	beautifully	7	7.6 ...
dole	18	7.7 ...	fruity	36	7.6 ...	powerfully	6	8.7 ...
blend	17	6.6 ...	full-bodied	34	8.2 ...	finely	6	8.2 ...
white	15	7.5 ...	complex	30	8.5 ...	softly	6	7.9 ...
acidity	14	4.5 ...	juicy	30	7.2 ...	broadly	5	8.9 ...
open	7	7.4 ...	balanced	28	8.1 ...	densely	5	7.8 ...

Figure 31. Collocates of “structured”

Figure 32. Collocations of “structured”.

Note: The illustration is depicting the collocations of “structured” with the nouns it modifies, also “and/or” collocates, as well as with its possessors. Typicality and Frequency are reflected as previously.

Going through the literature, “structure” refers to the balance of the five main characteristics of wine: *sweetness*, *acidity*, *tannin*, *alcohol*, *body*. According to an article published by Wine Folly (Puckette, n.d.), the meanings of these elements can be summarised as follows:

1. **Sweetness:** This term denotes the sugar content in wine, perceived on the tip of the tongue. Dry wines may also have a hint of sweetness.
2. **Acidity:** Acidity stimulates salivation, adding freshness to the wine. Wines with higher acidity feel lighter and spritzier.
3. **Tannin:** Tannin refers to the bitterness and astringency in wine, often manifesting as a drying sensation in the mouth. They add complexity and structure to the wine.
4. **Alcohol:** This is sensed as a warming sensation in the throat. The level of alcohol can affect a wine’s body and overall taste, making it taste bitter, sweet, spicy, or oily.
5. **Body:** Body is the overall impression of a wine, influenced by various factors including grape variety, origin, vintage, and alcohol level. It relates to the perceived heaviness or lightness of the wine on the palate.

Ultimately, the two most important factors in creating structure in a wine are acidity and tannins. Structure also plays a leading role in a wine’s ageability.

Wines with balanced structure have all of the elements to evolve harmoniously and gracefully over time (Saladino, 2020).

Overall, the results for the root “structure” align with literature descriptions of “structure” in wine, which refers to the balance of elements that contribute to the wine’s overall tasting experience. Based on this analysis, the word structure emerges as an important term for describing sensory attributes of wine.

Based on the above analyses, the five descriptors that were examined align closely with descriptions from online literature. Given their notable specificity, these terms likely warrant inclusion in a standardised set of terms.

4.4 Limitations

This kind of study inherently has several limitations. The main ones are mentioned below:

- Nature of the Dataset: The study is based on an existing, static dataset, which includes data for the period 2017-2020, so it could be outdated. The ideal scenario would involve scraping current data from various online sources maintaining a wine reviews database, and not only from Wine Enthusiast. Regrettably, access as well as time constraints prohibited doing so.
- Vocabulary Basis: The study primarily used WAW and WSET vocabularies as a basis for comparison. The inclusion or exclusion of other established wine vocabularies might lead to different insights.
- Selection of Terms:
 - a. The terms chosen for the DATAvoc vocabulary were selected arbitrarily, grounded on the criteria of their perceived relevance to olfaction, gustation, and tactility.
 - b. The study exclusively delved into the five most frequent terms, “juicy”, “dark”, “crisp”, “firm”, and “structured”. It's important to note that there are other potentially significant terms that were not analysed in this research.
- Reviewer Specialisation: The reviewers of the dataset have specialised expertise in specific wine-producing regions (Meet The Team, n.d.). Their vocabulary is likely shaped by the characteristics of wines from these particular areas. It's highly probable that such specialization among reviewers is a common practice in the industry. To enhance the accuracy of the results, a more diverse dataset from various sources would be beneficial.

Despite the aforementioned limitations, the results of this study are believed to representatively address the research questions.

5 Conclusion

This paper examined the context of wine reviews and in particular, the language used in them. It evaluated the extent to which reviewers adhere to standardised vocabularies and explored the implications of unique linguistic styles, or 'idiolects', on the consistency of such behaviour. Further, the research identified and analysed emergent, non-standard terms that possess the potential to augment the existing repertoire of standardised wine descriptors.

The quantitative analysis indicated that wine reviewers make substantial use of both WAW and WSET vocabularies, exhibiting relatively consistent linguistic patterns. Only two of the nineteen reviewers deviated from the overall pattern, displaying unique linguistic preferences that could potentially influence the overall results.

A total of 26.31% of the tokens in the dataset are non-standardised terms (NULLs). This frequency of NULL vocabulary usage further underscores the significance of non-standardised terms in wine reviews, contributing a sizeable portion of all terms used. These findings imply that while standardised vocabularies provide a helpful framework for wine communication, there remains considerable room for individual expression and creativity.

Through categorisation and analysis of NULL terms, the study revealed a remarkable diversity in the sensory impressions conveyed by reviewers, particularly those related to taste, flavour, aroma, and smell. Reviewers also frequently associated their sensory impressions with food and beverages, employing a wide variety of descriptive terms. This demonstrates that while standardised vocabularies provide a common language for wine reviewers, they may not fully capture the nuances and complexities of individual wine tasting experiences.

An in-depth analysis of the emergent terms “juicy”, “dark”, “crisp”, “firm”, and “structured” provided valuable insights into how these terms are used in wine reviews. Notably, these terms often refer to specific sensory characteristics, such as acidity, tannins, and balance, demonstrating the potential of non-standard terms in enhancing the expressiveness and precision of wine reviews.

This research contributes to the understanding of how professional reviewers communicate the wine-tasting experience. It highlights the balance between standardised and individual expression by providing an analysis of the language used in wine reviews. Furthermore, the study identifies potential terms that could enrich the established wine vocabularies.

Although it remains broadly consistent, the language of wine is also dynamic and continually evolving, reflecting the complex nature of the wine tasting experience itself. The language of wine, long dominated by European-centric terms, is lately being questioned and reassessed with the aim of becoming more inclusive, as the wine industry is beginning to acknowledge the need to engage with an ever-growing multicultural consumer base (Caputo, 2023; Lambert, 2023; Robinson, 2021). As

displayed throughout this study, the current descriptors of wine, are mainly based on fruit or taste references rooted deeply in European experiences and lifestyle.

Decolonising the wine lexicon means making it more accessible to people with culturally diverse food and taste experiences. Hence, research might therefore focus on how to translate wine flavours into descriptors reflecting this diversity of sensory experiences. There is a high likelihood that efforts are presently underway aiming to construct an alternative wine vocabulary with an emphasis on inclusivity. In this context, future research could focus on a more precise standardisation of wine terminology, in the form of controlled vocabularies.

Controlled vocabularies are organised collections of words and phrases, often related to a specific domain, used to index and retrieve content. They aim to standardise terminology, incorporating preferred terms and their variants, to improve consistency in cataloguing and information retrieval. These vocabularies collate synonyms and related concepts, sorting them into logical orders or categories to ensure well-defined, maintained connections for easier data categorisation and retrieval (Harpring, 2010). The wine language would benefit very much by such a system, especially in view of a wide opening to new descriptors. However, the complexity of this endeavour should not be underestimated. On one hand, wine tasting can carry a subjective element, often leading to diverse interpretations of the wine flavours. On the other hand, there would be a necessity for consensus on a single classification system, which might be challenging to achieve. Nevertheless, such an effort would be justified, representing a vital investment in preserving and enhancing the language of wine as a treasure of cultural heritage, thereby facilitating improved communication and appreciation for generations to come.

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Appendix 1

The Wine Aroma Wheel

Source: UC Davis Library (2021, December 5). *The Grape Professors of UC Davis*. From Vine To Wine: Highlights From Special Collections. Retrieved August 11, 2023, from <https://scalar.usc.edu/works/from-vine-to-wine/ann-c-noble>

Appendix 2

WAWvoc

Acetaldehyde	Cool	Linalool	Strawberry
Acetate	Cork	Match	Sulfide
Acetic	Currant	Melon	Sulfur
Acid	Cut	Menthol	Sulfur dioxide
Alcohol	Diacetyl	Mercaptan	Sweaty
Almond	Diesel	Methyl	Tar
Anise	Dioxide	Microbiological	Tea
Anthranilate	Dog	Mildew	Toast
Apple	Dried	Mint	Tobacco
Apricot	Dusty	Molasses	Tree
Artichoke	Earthy	Moldy	Tropical
Artificial	Ethanol	Mushroom	Vanilla
Asparagus	Ethyl	Musty	Vegetative
Banana	Eucalyptus	Nutty	Violet
Beans	Fig	Oak	Walnut
Bell	Filter	Olive	Wet
Berry	Floral	Orange	Wood
Black	Flor	Oxidized	Wool
Blackberry	Fresh	Pad	Yeast
Blossom	Fruit	Papery	
Burned	Fruity	Peach	
Burnt	Fusel	Pepper	
Butter	Garlic	Petroleum	
Butterscotch	Geranium	Phenolic	
Butyric	Grapefruit	Plastic	
Cabbage	Grass	Prune	
Canned	Green	Pungent	
Caramel	Hay	Raisin	
Caramelized	Hazelnut	Resinous	
Cardboard	Herbaceous	Rose	
Cassis	Honey	Rubbery	
Cedar	Horsey	Sauerkraut	
Charred	Hot	Skunk	
Chemical	Hydrogen	Smoky	
Cherry	Jam	Soapy	
Chocolate	Kerosene	Sorbate	
Citrus	Lactic	Soy sauce	
Cloves	Leesy	Spicy	
Coffee	Lemon	Stemmy	
Cooked	Licorice	Straw	

Appendix 3

WSET Level 4 Systematic Approach to Tasting Wine®

APPEARANCE

Intensity	pale – medium – deep
Colour	white lemon – gold – amber – brown rosé pink – pink-orange – orange red purple – ruby – garnet – tawny

NOSE

Intensity	light – medium(-) – medium – medium(+) – pronounced
Aroma characteristics	e.g. primary, secondary, tertiary

PALATE

Sweetness	dry – off-dry – medium-dry – medium-sweet – sweet
Acidity	low – medium(-) – medium – medium(+) – high
Tannin	level low – medium(-) – medium – medium(+) – high nature e.g. ripe, soft, smooth, unripe, green, coarse, stalky, chalky, fine-grained
Alcohol	low – medium – high
Body	light – medium(-) – medium – medium(+) – full
Flavour intensity	light – medium(-) – medium – medium(+) – pronounced
Flavour characteristics	e.g. primary, secondary, tertiary
Other observations	e.g. texture (e.g. oily, creamy, austere, luscious), pétillance (still wines only)
Finish	short – medium(-) – medium – medium(+) – long

CONCLUSIONS

Quality assessment	poor – acceptable – good – very good – outstanding (an explanation supporting the assessment of a wine's quality will be required)
Bottle ageing	suitable for bottle ageing – not suitable for bottle ageing (an explanation supporting the assessment of a wine's suitability for bottle ageing will be required)

Notes to students:

For lines where the entries are separated by a hyphen – You must select one and only one of these options.

For lines starting with 'e.g.' where the entries are separated with commas – These are entries that you should consider when writing your tasting note. You may not need to comment on each entry for every wine.

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WSET Level 4 Wine-Lexicon:

supporting the WSET Level 4 Systematic Approach to Tasting Wine®

DESCRIBING AROMA AND FLAVOUR

Primary Aromas and Flavours

The aromas and flavours of the grape and alcoholic fermentation

Floral	blossom, elderflower, honeysuckle, jasmine, rose, violet
Green fruit	apple, pear, gooseberry, grape
Citrus fruit	grapefruit, lemon, lime, orange
Stone fruit	peach, apricot, nectarine
Tropical fruit	banana, lychee, mango, melon, passion fruit, pineapple
Red fruit	redcurrant, cranberry, raspberry, strawberry, red cherry, red plum
Black fruit	blackcurrant, blackberry, blueberry, black cherry, black plum
Herbaceous	green bell pepper (capsicum), grass, tomato leaf, asparagus
Herbal	eucalyptus, mint, fennel, dill, dried herbs (e.g. thyme, oregano)
Spice	black/white pepper, liquorice, cinnamon
Fruit ripeness	unripe fruit, ripe fruit, dried fruit, cooked fruit
Other	e.g. simple, wet stones, candy

Secondary Aromas and Flavours

The aromas and flavours of post-fermentation winemaking

Yeast (lees, autolysis, flor)	biscuit/graham cracker, bread, toasted bread, pastry, brioche, bread dough, cheese, yogurt, acetaldehyde
Malolactic conversion	butter, cream, cheese
Oak	vanilla, cloves, coconut, cedar, charred wood, smoke, chocolate, coffee

Tertiary Aromas and Flavours

The aromas and flavours of maturation

Red wine	dried fruit (e.g. prune, raisin, fig), cooked fruit (e.g. cooked plum, cooked cherry), leather, earth, mushroom, meat, tobacco, wet leaves, forest floor, caramel
White wine	dried fruit (e.g. dried apricot, raisin) orange marmalade, petrol (gasoline), cinnamon, ginger, nutmeg, almond, hazelnut, honey, caramel
Deliberately oxidised wines	almond, hazelnut, walnut, chocolate, coffee, caramel

Note to students:

The WSET Level 4 Wine-Lexicon is designed to be a prompt and a guide which you do not need to memorise. You can pass the tasting examination if you use the descriptors in the Wine-Lexicon but you do not need to limit yourself to these terms and the examiners will accept other descriptors so long as they are accurate.

Source: *WSET Level 4 Systematic Approach to Tasting Wine*®. (2023). Retrieved August 9, 2023, from Wine & Spirit Education Trust: https://www.wsetglobal.com/media/13271/wset_l4wines_sat_en_aug2023.pdf

Appendix 4

WSETvoc

acacia	brioche	drop	intensity	oak	stewed
acidity	butter	dry	jamminess	orange	stone
age	butterscotch	earth	juice	overripe	stones
ageability	capsicum	elderflower	kerosene	oxidation	sultana
ageable	caramel	eucalyptus	kirsch	palate	sweetness
aged	cedar	farmyard	lavender	passion	tannin
ageing	chamomile	fennel	leaf	pastry	tar
ageless	charred	fig	leather	peach	tertiary
ageworthiness	cheese	finish	leaves	pear	tired
ageworthy	cherry	flint	lees	peel	toast
aggressive	chocolate	floor	lemon	pepper	tobacco
alcohol	cinnamon	floral	lemon peel	petrol	toffee
almond	citrus	forest	licorice	pineapple	tomato
apple	clean	fresh	lime	plum	tropical
apricot	cloves	fruit	luscious	preserved	unclean
apricot	coconut	fruits	lychee	primary	underripe
asparagus	coffee	game	malolactic	prune	vanilla
autolysis	complex	generic	mango	pungent	vegetal
baked	conversion	geranium	marmalade	quince	violet
banana	cooked	ginger	marzipan	raisin	walnut
bell	cranberry	gooseberry	meaty	red	wet
biscuit	creamy	grape	medicinal	redcurrant	white
black	defined	grapefruit	melon	resinous	wood
blackberry	delicate	grass	mint	ripe	wool
blackcurrant	developed	green	mousse	rose	yeast
blossom	developing	hay	mushroom	savoury	youthful
blueberry	development	hazelnut	nectarine	secondary	zest
body	dill	herbaceous	nose	simple	
bramble	dough	herbal	nutmeg	smoke	
bread	dried	honeysuckle	nutty	spice	

Appendix 5

DATAvoc

abrasive	amaro	bacony	beans
acacia	amarone	bacteria	beef
acai	ammonia	baguette	beefsteak
acetic	angelfood	bailey	beefy
acetone	anglaise	baked	beer
acid	angostura	baker	beery
acidic	anise	bakers	beeswax
acidity	aniseed	bakery	beet
acids	aniseseasonings	baking	beetroot
afterburn	anisettes	balloon	beets
afternotes	aperol	balm	bell
aftertaste	apple	balminess	benedictine
age	applejacks	balmy	bergamot
ageability	apples	balsam	berries
ageable	applesauce	balsamic	berry
aged	applewood	bamboo	berryish
ageing	appley	banana	berrylicious
ageless	apricot	bananas	berrylike
ageworthiness	apricots	band	birch
ageworthy	argan	bandage	biscotti
aggression	argyle	bandages	biscuit
aggressive	armagnac	barbecue	biscuits
aggressiveness	armpit	barbecued	biscuity
aging	artemia	barbecues	bismol
aid	artichoke	barbeque	bitter
aids	artificial	barn	bitterness
alcohol	arugula	barnyard	bitterroot
alcoholic	ash	barnyardy	bitters
alfalfa	ashtray	barrel	bittersweet
alkaline	ashy	barrels	black
alkalinity	asparagus	basalt	blackberries
allium	asphalt	basket	blackberry
alloro	astringency	baskets	blackcurrant
allspice	astringent	bay	blood
almond	astute	bayleaf	bloodwort
almonds	autolysis	bbq	bloody
almondy	autolytic	beachgrass	bloom
aloe	baby	beachside	bloomer
alpha	babys	bean	blooming
amarena	bacon	beanoy	blooms

blossom	brick	calcareous	cask
blossoms	bricks	calendula	casks
blossomy	brie	camomile	casserole
blue	brine	camp	cassis
blueberries	briney	campfire	cassoulet
blueberry	briny	camphor	cat
bluegrass	brioche	candia	catalan
boar	broccoli	candied	catmint
bodied	broiled	candies	cattle
body	brokenwood	candle	cattleman
boiled	bronze	candlewax	catty
bonbon	brownie	candy	cauliflower
botanical	brownies	candylike	cayenne
botanicals	brulee	cane	cedar
botrytis	bubblegum	cannabis	cedary
botrytized	burn	canned	celery
bouillon	burning	cannellini	cement
bouquet	burns	cantaloupe	cements
bouquets	burnt	caper	ceramic
bourbon	burritos	capers	cereal
box	butter	cappuccino	ceviche
boxed	butterball	cappuccio	chalk
boxes	buttercream	caramel	chalkboard
boxwood	buttercup	caramelization	chalkiness
boysenberries	buttercups	caramelized	chalky
boysenberry	buttered	caraway	challah
bramble	butterfat	carbon	chamomile
brambleberry	butterfinger	carbonation	chaparral
bramblebush	butteriness	carbonic	char
brambles	buttermilk	cardamom	charcoal
bramblier	butterscotch	cardboard	charcuterie
bran	butterscotchy	carnation	charred
brandy	buttery	carnations	charry
brash	cabbage	carob	cheddar
brashness	cabbagey	carpaccio	cheese
brassy	cactus	carrot	cheeseburgers
bread	cake	carrots	cheesecake
breadcrumb	cakebread	cashew	cheeses
bready	caked	cashews	cheesy
brettanomyces	cakes	cashmere	chemical

chemicals	cigarette	cocoa	cooking
cherries	cigars	coconut	cool
cherry	cilantro	coconutty	cooler
cherryish	ciliegiolo	coffee	coolers
cherrylike	cinnamon	coffees	coolest
cherrywood	cinnamony	cognac	cooley
chester	cipresso	cointreau	cooling
chestnut	citric	cola	coolish
chew	citron	colada	coolness
chewier	citronella	collognes	copper
chewiness	citrus	cologne	coppermine
chewy	citrusy	complex	coppery
chicken	clafoutis	complexify	coquelicot
chicory	clam	complexion	coral
chili	clammy	complexities	coriander
chilies	clay	complexity	cork
chimichurri	clean	complexly	corks
chimney	cleaner	compost	corn
chipotle	cleanest	compostable	cornbread
chive	cleaning	composted	cornmeal
chives	cleanliness	composty	corral
chlorine	cleanly	composure	corrals
chock	cleanness	compote	cotta
chockful	cleans	confect	cotton
chocolate	cleanse	confected	cottony
chocolaty	cleanser	confection	cough
chops	cleanses	confectioners	coulis
chrysanthemum	cleansing	confectionery	countryside
chunk	clementine	confections	crab
chunkier	clementines	confit	crabapple
chunkiness	clove	confiture	cracker
chunks	clover	conifer	crackers
chunky	cloves	coniferous	cran
churro	co	conserve	cranberries
ciabatta	co2	conserves	cranberry
cider	coal	consomme	cranberryish
cidercast	cobb	cook	cream
cidery	cobbler	cooked	creamed
cigar	cobblestone	cookie	creamier
cigarbox	coco	cookies	creaminess

creamsicle	curranty	delicious	dustier
creamy	curries	deliciousness	dustiness
crema	curry	dense	dusting
cremant	curvaceous	denseness	dustings
creme	curve	denser	dusts
creosote	curves	densest	dusty
cress	curvier	densities	earth
crisp	curvy	density	earthbound
crispens	custard	depth	earthen
crisper	custardy	depths	earthier
crispest	cutlets	desiccated	earthiness
crisply	cypress	desiccation	earthy
crispness	daffodil	dessert	edge
crispy	daffodils	desserts	edged
croissant	daiquiri	destemmed	edges
croissants	dairy	develop	edgier
crop	daisies	developed	edginess
crops	daisy	developer	edgings
crouton	damp	developing	edgy
crumble	dampen	development	egg
crumbles	dampened	develops	eggnog
crumbs	dampening	dijon	eggplant
crunch	dampens	dill	eggs
crunches	dandelion	dioxide	eggy
crunchier	dandelions	dog	elastic
crunchiness	dark	dogs	elasticity
crunchy	darkchocolaty	donkey	elderberries
crust	darkens	dough	elderberry
crusty	darker	doughnut	elderflower
cucumber	darkest	doughy	elderflowers
cumin	darkish	dried	elk
cupcake	darkly	driftwood	equestrian
curacao	darkness	dry	espresso
curant	date	dryer	eucalypt
curd	dates	drying	eucalyptus
curds	decadence	dryish	evergreen
cure	decadent	dryly	exotic
cured	deer	dryness	exoticism
currant	delicate	dust	extract
currants	delicatessen	dusted	fajitas

farm	field	fleuries	freshen
farmed	fields	fleury	freshened
farmer	fig	flint	freshener
farmers	figgy	flintiness	freshens
farmhouse	figs	flinty	fresher
farming	filet	floor	freshess
farms	filo	floorboards	freshest
farmstand	filter	floors	freshly
farmworkers	filtered	flor	freshness
farmyard	filtration	flora	fries
farmyardy	finish	floral	fruit
fat	finishes	florality	fruitcake
fatness	finishing	florals	fruited
fattened	fir	flour	fruitedness
fattens	fire	flourish	fruitier
fatter	firepit	flourishes	fruitiest
fatty	fireplace	flower	fruitiness
fault	fires	flowering	fruitless
faultline	fireside	flowers	fruitpunch
faults	firethorn	flowery	fruits
faulty	firewood	focaccia	fruity
feinherb	firm	foliage	frutti
feline	firmer	forest	fry
fennel	firmly	forested	fudge
fenugreek	firmness	forests	fudges
feral	fish	foresty	fudginess
ferment	fishy	fossil	fudgy
fermentation	fivespice	fossils	fuel
fermentations	flaw	fowl	fuels
fermentative	flawless	fox	fumes
fermented	flaws	foxen	fungus
fermenter	flesh	foxiness	furry
fermenters	fleshed	foxs	game
fermenting	fleshes	foxy	gamelike
ferments	fleshier	fraiche	gamier
fern	fleshiness	framboise	gaminess
ferns	fleshing	frangipani	gamy
ferrets	fleshy	frankincense	ganache
fetel	fleur	freesia	garden
fettuccine	fleurie	fresh	gardenia

gardenias	grains	grounds	heads
gardens	grainy	grove	heady
garlic	granita	guava	heart
garlicky	granite	gum	hearted
garnet	granitic	gumball	heartedness
garrigue	grape	gumdrop	hearth
gaseous	grapefruit	gummed	heartier
gasoline	grapefruits	gummies	heartiness
gassy	grapefruity	gummy	heartly
gatorade	grapenut	gums	heat
gauze	grapenuts	gun	heavier
gauzy	grapes	gunmetal	heaviest
gelato	grapeseed	gunpowder	heavily
geranium	grapeseeds	guns	heaviness
geraniums	grapeskin	gush	heavy
ghee	grapey	gushes	heavyset
gin	graphite	gushy	heavyweight
ginger	grapy	hair	hedgehog
gingerbread	grass	halibut	hedgerow
gingered	grasses	ham	hedges
gingerly	grassiness	hamburger	herb
gingersnap	grassy	hamburgers	herbaceous
gingersnaps	gravel	hawthorn	herbaceousness
gingery	gravelly	hay	herbal
gingko	gravels	hayflower	herbality
glaze	gravy	hayflowers	herbed
glazed	grease	hays	herbes
gluten	greasy	haystack	herbs
glycerine	green	haystacks	herby
glycerol	greener	hazel	hersheys
gooey	greenery	hazelnut	hibiscus
goose	greengage	hazelnuts	hickory
gooseberries	greengages	hazelnutty	hoisin
gooseberry	greenish	head	honey
gouda	greenness	headed	honeybush
graham	greens	headfirst	honeycomb
grahams	grenadine	headier	honeycrisp
grain	grill	headiest	honeydew
grained	grilled	headiness	honeyed
graininess	ground	heading	honeylike

honeysuckle	jam	lasagna	lime
horse	jambon	latex	limes
horseradish	jammier	latte	limestone
horses	jamminess	laurel	limey
horsey	jammy	laurelwood	linen
hot	jasmine	lavender	lingonberry
huckleberries	jell	leaf	linguine
huckleberry	jellies	leafier	lipton
hum	jells	leafiness	liqueur
humidor	jelly	leafy	liquor
humus	jerky	lean	liquorous
hyacinth	jicama	leaner	loaf
incense	juice	leanness	loam
incensed	juiced	leather	loamy
infuse	juices	leathery	lobster
infused	juicier	leaves	loganberries
infuses	juiciest	leek	loganberry
infusing	juicily	lees	lola
infusion	juiciness	leesiness	lollipop
infusions	juicy	leesy	long
ink	jujube	lemon	longer
inkier	juniper	lemonade	longest
inkily	kaffir	lemongrass	lotion
inkwell	kahlua	lemongrassy	louisa
inky	kale	lemonhead	lozenge
intense	kernel	lemons	lumber
intensified	kerosene	lemony	lumbery
intensifies	kimchee	length	lychee
intensify	kirsch	lengthen	lychees
intensifying	kiwi	lengthens	macadamia
intensities	kiwifruit	lengthiness	macaroon
intensity	kumquat	lengths	macaroons
intensive	lacquer	lengthy	madeleine
iodine	lactic	lentil	magnolia
iris	lactis	lettuce	mahogany
iron	lactones	licorice	malo
ironstone	lait	lilac	malolactic
ivy	lamb	lilacs	malt
jalapeno	lanolin	lilies	malty
jalapenos	lanoline	lily	mandarin

mandarins	medicinality	morello	noodles
mango	medicine	moss	nose
mangos	melba	mossy	noseful
manzana	mellifluous	mouse	noses
manzanilla	melon	mousiness	nosing
manzanillas	melons	mousse	nougat
maple	melony	mousy	nut
mapley	melrose	mouth	nutella
maraschino	menthol	mud	nutmeg
margarita	mentholated	mudd	nuts
margaritas	meringue	muddies	nuttier
marigold	mescal	muddy	nuttiness
marigolds	mesquite	muffin	nutty
marijuana	metal	mulberries	oak
marinade	metallic	mulberry	oaked
marinara	midpalate	mulch	oakier
marinates	milk	mulchy	oakiness
marionberries	milkiness	multivitamin	oakleaf
marionberry	milkshake	mushroom	oaks
marjoram	milkweed	mushrooms	oaky
marmalade	milky	mushroomy	oat
marron	mimosa	musk	oatmeal
marshmallow	mimosas	muskiness	oil
marshmallows	mincemeat	muskmelon	oilier
marshmallowy	mineral	musky	oiliness
martini	minerality	mussel	oils
marzipan	minerals	mussels	oily
matcha	minestrone	mustard	olallieberries
matchbook	mint	mustardy	olallieberry
matchbox	mints	myrrh	old
matches	minty	myrtle	older
matchstick	mirabelle	narcissus	oldest
matchsticky	mirabelles	nectar	olive
meat	miso	nectarine	olives
meatballs	mocha	nectarines	olivey
meatier	mochaflavors	nectarous	onion
meatiness	molasses	nectars	onions
meats	molassesy	nesquik	oniony
meaty	mold	nestea	orange
medicinal	morel	noodle	orangeade

oranges	patisserie	peppery	pizay
orangesicle	pea	perfume	pizazz
orangey	peach	perfumed	pizza
orangish	peaches	perfumery	plank
orangy	peachier	perfumes	planks
orchard	peachiest	perfuming	planky
orchards	peachiness	perfumy	plaster
oregano	peachy	petal	plastic
oud	peanut	petals	plasticky
overoaked	peanutbrittle	petrol	plum
oxidation	peanuts	petroleum	plummier
oxidative	pear	phenol	plumminess
oxide	pearfruit	phenolic	plummy
oxidization	pears	phenolics	plums
oxidized	peas	pickle	plunk
oxygen	peashoot	pickled	poached
oxygenation	peasy	pickles	polyethylene
oyster	peat	pie	pomegranate
oysters	peatiness	piecrust	pomegranates
oystershell	pebble	pig	pomelo
ozonic	pebbles	pigeon	pop
paella	pecan	pigs	popcorn
palate	pecans	pimenton	poplar
palates	pecorino	pimiento	poppy
papaya	pee	pimpernel	poppyseed
paper	peel	pine	popside
papery	peels	pineapple	porcini
paprika	pekoe	pineapples	pork
paraffin	pencil	pineapplely	porky
parsley	pencils	pinecone	potato
parsnip	peony	pinetrees	potatoes
parsnips	pepper	pinetrees	potpourri
passion	peppercorn	pipe	powder
passionfruit	peppercorns	pipestone	powdered
pasta	peppered	pistachio	powdery
pastas	pepperiness	pistachios	praline
pastrami	peppering	pith	pralines
pastries	peppermint	pithier	prawns
pastry	pepperoni	pithiness	pretzel
patchouli	peppers	pithy	primary

prosciutto	resiny	sagebrush	savoriness
prune	rhubarb	sagey	savory
prunes	ribena	sake	saw
pruney	rind	salad	sawdust
pruny	rinds	salads	sawmill
pudding	roast	salami	scallion
pumpernickel	roasted	saline	scallions
pumpkin	roasts	salinity	scallops
punch	roasty	salmon	schist
punchy	rock	salmonberries	schisty
pungency	rocks	salmonberry	scones
pungent	rocky	salt	scrub
pyrazine	rooibos	salted	scrubbing
pyrazines	root	saltine	sea
pyrazinic	rooted	saltines	seabreeze
quince	roots	saltiness	seafoam
quincy	rootstock	salts	seafood
quinine	rootstocks	saltwater	seafoods
ragout	rooty	salty	seas
raisin	roquefort	salumi	seashell
raisinated	roquette	sandalwood	seashells
raisins	rose	sandpaper	seaside
raisiny	rosebud	sandpapery	seasoning
rasp	rosebuds	sandstone	seasonings
raspberries	rosehip	sandy	seaspray
raspberry	rosemary	sanguine	secondary
raspy	roses	sappiness	seltzer
raw	rosewater	sappy	sesame
rawness	rubber	sarsaparilla	shallot
red	rubberband	satsuma	shallots
redberry	rubbery	sauce	shape
redcherry	rust	sauced	shaped
redcurrant	rustiness	sauced	shapeless
redwood	rusty	sauciness	shapes
redwoods	rye	saucy	sharp
residual	saccharine	sauerkraut	sharpens
residuals	sachet	sausage	sharper
residue	saddle	sausages	sharpness
resin	saffron	sauteed	sharpy
resinous	sage	savor	shea

shell	snickers	sprinklings	structuring
shellfish	soap	spruce	strudel
shells	soapiness	squid	suede
sherbet	soaps	stalk	sugar
sherbety	soapstone	stalkiness	sugarcane
shiitake	soapy	stalks	sugared
shiitakes	sock	stalky	sugariness
shortbread	socks	starch	sugarloaf
shortcrust	soda	starched	sugarplum
shotgun	sodalike	starching	sugars
shrimp	soft	starchy	sugary
shrub	soil	starfruit	sulfite
shrubbiness	soils	steakhouse	sulfites
shrubby	sorbet	steaks	sulfur
shrubs	souffle	steal	sulfuric
shy	soup	steel	sulfurous
shyer	soupy	stem	sulphur
shyly	sour	stemminess	sulphuric
shyness	sourball	stemmy	sultana
silicon	sourdough	stems	sultanas
skin	sourness	stew	sumac
skinned	soy	stewed	sunbaked
skins	spaghetti	stews	sundae
skinsy	spearmint	stewy	sushi
slate	spice	stinky	sweat
slater	spicebox	stone	sweatiness
slatey	spiced	stonefruit	sweaty
slurp	spices	stones	sweet
slushie	spicier	stoney	sweetbread
smarties	spiciest	stonier	sweeten
smoke	spiciness	stoniness	sweetened
smoked	spicing	stony	sweetens
smoker	spicy	stout	sweeter
smokes	spinach	straw	sweetest
smokey	sponge	strawberries	sweetgrass
smokier	spongy	strawberry	sweetish
smokiness	sprinkle	structural	sweetness
smoky	sprinkled	structure	sweets
smoothie	sprinkles	structured	swirl
snickerdoodle	sprinkling	structures	swirling

swirls	teriyaki	umami	watercress
syrup	terracotta	uric	watermelon
syrups	tertiary	vanilla	watermelons
syrupy	thai	vanillan	wax
szechuan	thimbleberries	vanillin	waxed
tabasco	thistle	vaseline	waxen
tablets	thyme	vegemite	waxes
tacos	tiramisu	vegetable	waxiness
tagine	tired	vegetables	waxy
tahini	tiredness	vegetal	weeds
talc	tisane	vegetation	weedy
talcum	toast	vegetative	wet
tamarind	toasted	veggie	wheat
tang	toastier	veggies	wheatgrass
tangerine	toastiness	veggy	wheaty
tangerines	toasts	venison	whiskey
tangs	toasty	verbena	whisky
tangy	tobacco	vermouth	whopper
tannic	toffee	vietnamese	wildfire
tannin	tofu	vinaigrette	wildflower
tannina	tomato	vine	wildflowers
tanninic	tomatoes	vinegar	willow
tannins	tomatoey	vinegary	wisteria
tannish	torte	vines	wood
tapas	tortilla	vinosity	wooden
tapenade	tree	vinyl	woodier
tar	trees	violet	woodiness
tarmac	tropical	violets	woodland
tarragon	tropicality	viscosity	woodlands
tarriness	truffle	viscous	woodruff
tarry	truffles	vitamin	woods
tart	tuberose	vitamins	woodsmoke
tartare	tulip	wafer	woodspice
tartaric	tulips	waffle	woody
tarte	turf	waffles	woody
tartine	turkey	wallflower	wool
tartness	turmeric	wallflowers	woolsey
tatin	turnip	walnut	wooly
tea	turpentine	walnuts	workhorse
tenderloin	tutti	walnutty	wreath

wreathed
wreaths
yeast
yeastiness
yeasts
yeasty
yeastyness
yogurt
young
younger
youngest
youth
youthful
youthfulness
zest
zestier
zestiest
zestiness
zesty
zing
zinger
zingiest
zinginess
zings
zingy
zucchini

Appendix 6

Programme codes in Python and Excel Spreadsheet:

CODE 1: This code takes as input file MasterDataset2.csv and reads the first 1000 bytes of it, and using chardet library detects the encoding. The dataset was also tested at several points other than the first 100.000 bytes.

```
import chardet

# Open the file in binary mode
with open('MasterDataset2.csv', 'rb') as f:
    # Read the first 100000 bytes of the file for detection
    rawdata = f.read(100000)

# Detect the encoding of the file
result = chardet.detect(rawdata)

# Print the detected encoding
print(result['encoding'])
```

CODE 2: This code takes as input file “MasterDataset2.csv” and using the codecs module, it reads it as Windows-1252. Then it writes the output in file “MasterDataset3.csv”, with UTF-8 encoding. The delimiter and quotechar parameters specify the delimiter and quote character used in the CSV file. The quoting parameter is set to csv.QUOTE_MINIMAL, which means that only the fields containing special characters or line breaks will be enclosed in quotes.

```
import csv
import codecs

filename = 'MasterDataset2.csv'
output_filename = 'MasterDataset3.csv'
encoding = 'Windows-1252'

with codecs.open(filename, 'r', encoding) as input_file, \
    codecs.open(output_filename, 'w', encoding='utf-8') as \
output_file:

    reader = csv.reader(input_file, delimiter=',',
quotechar='"', quoting=csv.QUOTE_MINIMAL)
    writer = csv.writer(output_file, delimiter=',',
quotechar='"', quoting=csv.QUOTE_MINIMAL)

    for row in reader:
        writer.writerow(row)
```

CODE 3: This code takes as input file “MasterDataset3.csv” and performs text preprocessing and frequency counting tasks on it: converts words to lowercase, joins row elements, replaces dashes with spaces, removes punctuation, tokenizes and removes stopwords. The preprocessed tokens are written to the “preprocessed file”. The code counts the frequency of appearance for each token in the preprocessed file, and writes the token-frequency pairs to the frequency count file.

```
import csv
import string
import nltk
from nltk.corpus import stopwords
from nltk.tokenize import word_tokenize
from nltk import pos_tag
from collections import Counter

# Download necessary NLTK resources
nltk.download('averaged_perceptron_tagger')
nltk.download('stopwords')
nltk.download('punkt')

# Define input and output file paths
input_file = 'MasterDataset3.csv'
preprocessed_file = 'MasterDataset3_preprocessed.csv'
frequency_file = 'MasterDataset3_frequency.csv'

# Load stop words
stop_words = set(stopwords.words('english'))

# Open input file and preprocessed file for writing
with open(input_file, 'r', encoding='latin-1') as f, \
    open(preprocessed_file, 'w', newline='', encoding='utf-8') as f2:

    # Create a CSV reader and writer objects
    reader = csv.reader(f)
    writer = csv.writer(f2)

    # Iterate over each row in the input file
    for row in reader:
        # Convert to lowercase
        row = [word.lower() for word in row]

        # Join row elements to form a single string
        row = ' '.join(row)

        # Replace dash with space and remove punctuation
        row = row.replace('-', ' ')
        row = row.translate(str.maketrans('', '', string.punctuation))

        # Tokenize and remove stop words
        tokens = word_tokenize(row)
```

```
        tokens = [word for word in tokens if not word in
stop_words]

        # Write preprocessed data to file
        writer.writerow(tokens)

# Open preprocessed file for reading and frequency count file
for writing
with open(preprocessed_file, 'r', encoding='utf-8') as f, \
    open(frequency_file, 'w', newline='', encoding='utf-8')
as f2:

    # Create a CSV reader and writer objects
    reader = csv.reader(f)
    writer = csv.writer(f2)

    # Count frequency of appearance of each token
    frequency = Counter()
    for row in reader:
        frequency.update(row)

    # Write frequency count data to file
    writer.writerow(['Token', 'Frequency'])
    for token, count in frequency.items():
        writer.writerow([token, count])

# Print output
#print('Preprocessed data:')

#with open(preprocessed_file, 'r', encoding='utf-8') as f:
    #print(f.read())

print('The process is over')
```

CODE 4: This code takes as input file “DATAvoc_frequency.csv” and a vocabulary file (“WAWvoc.csv” or “WSETvoc.csv”), checks if the tokens from the first file exist in the vocabulary and writes the processed data to a new .csv file, including the token, frequency and a “YES” or “NO” value indicating whether the token is present in the vocabulary set.

```
import csv

# Open input files
with open('DATAvoc_frequency.csv', newline='') as csvfile1, \
    open('WAWvoc.csv', newline='') as csvfile2, \
    open('WAW_Result.csv', 'w', newline='') as output_file:

    # Create CSV reader objects
    reader1 = csv.reader(csvfile1)
    reader2 = csv.reader(csvfile2)

    # Create CSV writer object
    writer = csv.writer(output_file)

    # Create set to store WAW vocabulary
    waw_voc = set()
    for row in reader2:
        waw_voc.add(row[0])

    # Write header row to output file
    writer.writerow(['token', 'frequency', 'WAW'])

    # Process each row in DATAvoc_frequency.csv
    for row in reader1:
        token = row[0]
        freq = row[1]
        waw = 'YES' if token in waw_voc else 'NO'
        writer.writerow([token, freq, waw])
```

Comparison Spreadsheet link:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1nvjuATYk8eXEF40aXzymIH1ljS0d6P87/edit?usp=sharing&oid=104493436601510445237&rtpof=true&sd=true>

Sample:

TOKEN	FREQUENCY	WAW	final WAW	WSET	final WSET	Comparison
abrasive	96	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
acacia	254	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
acai	22	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
acetic	7	YES	YES	NO	NO	WAW
acetone	2	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
acid	624	YES	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET
acidic	462	NO	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET
acidity	24597	NO	YES	YES	YES	WAW/WSET
acids	243	NO	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET
afterburn	1	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
afternotes	2	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
aftertaste	1456	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
age	3247	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET
ageability	26	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET
ageable	3	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET
aged	153	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET
ageing	1	NO	NO	YES	YES	WSET
ageless	1	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET
ageworthiness	3	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET
ageworthy	140	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET
aggression	1	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
aggressive	218	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
aggressiveness	2	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
aging	22	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET
aid	99	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
aids	2	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
alcohol	856	YES	YES	YES	YES	WAW/WSET
alcoholic	72	NO	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET
alfalfa	5	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
alkaline	5	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
alkalinity	2	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
allium	3	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
alloro	3	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
allspice	131	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL
almond	1625	YES	YES	YES	YES	WAW/WSET
almonds	105	NO	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET

WAW	final WAW	WSET	final WSET	WAW/WSET	NULL
0	0	0	0	0	96
0	0	0	0	0	254
0	0	0	0	0	22
7	7	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	2
624	624	0	624	624	0
0	462	0	462	462	0
0	24597	24597	24597	24597	0
0	243	0	243	243	0
0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	1456
0	0	0	3247	0	0
0	0	0	26	0	0
0	0	0	3	0	0
0	0	0	153	0	0
0	0	1	1	0	0
0	0	0	1	0	0
0	0	0	3	0	0
0	0	0	140	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	218
0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	22	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	99
0	0	0	0	0	2
856	856	856	856	856	0
0	72	0	72	72	0
0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	5
0	0	0	0	0	2
0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	3
0	0	0	0	0	131
1625	1625	1625	1625	1625	0
0	105	0	105	105	0

CODE 5- 19: This code is similar to CODE 3 but takes as input 19 files, one for each reviewer and generates separate preprocessed and frequency count files for each input file. Specifically, it converts words to lowercase, joins row elements, replaces dashes with spaces, removes punctuation, tokenizes, removes stopwords and numbers. Then it writes the preprocessed tokens in 19 corresponding preprocessed files. Subsequently, it counts the frequency of appearance for each token in the preprocessed files and writes the frequency count data, consisting of token-frequency pairs, to 19 output files. Throughout the process, the code iterates over each input file, applies the preprocessing and frequency counting steps and generates separate output files for each input file. After processing each file, it prints the progress information, indicating the current file number out of the total number of input files.

```
import csv
import string
import nltk
from nltk.corpus import stopwords
from nltk.tokenize import word_tokenize
from collections import Counter
import re

# Download necessary NLTK resources
nltk.download('stopwords')
nltk.download('punkt')

# Define input and output file paths
input_files = ['N1.csv', 'N2.csv', 'N3.csv', 'N4.csv',
               'N5.csv', 'N6.csv', 'N7.csv', 'N8.csv', 'N9.csv', 'N10.csv',
               'N11.csv', 'N12.csv', 'N13.csv', 'N14.csv', 'N15.csv',
               'N16.csv', 'N17.csv', 'N18.csv', 'N19.csv']
preprocessed_files = ['N1_preprocessed.csv',
                      'N2_preprocessed.csv', 'N3_preprocessed.csv',
                      'N4_preprocessed.csv', 'N5_preprocessed.csv',
                      'N6_preprocessed.csv', 'N7_preprocessed.csv',
                      'N8_preprocessed.csv', 'N9_preprocessed.csv',
                      'N10_preprocessed.csv', 'N11_preprocessed.csv',
                      'N12_preprocessed.csv', 'N13_preprocessed.csv',
                      'N14_preprocessed.csv', 'N15_preprocessed.csv',
                      'N16_preprocessed.csv', 'N17_preprocessed.csv',
                      'N18_preprocessed.csv', 'N19_preprocessed.csv']
frequency_files = ['N1_frequency.csv', 'N2_frequency.csv',
                   'N3_frequency.csv', 'N4_frequency.csv', 'N5_frequency.csv',
                   'N6_frequency.csv', 'N7_frequency.csv', 'N8_frequency.csv',
                   'N9_frequency.csv', 'N10_frequency.csv', 'N11_frequency.csv',
                   'N12_frequency.csv', 'N13_frequency.csv',
                   'N14_frequency.csv', 'N15_frequency.csv',
                   'N16_frequency.csv', 'N17_frequency.csv',
                   'N18_frequency.csv', 'N19_frequency.csv']

# Load stop words
```

```

stop_words = set(stopwords.words('english'))

# Preprocess each input file and write preprocessed data to
corresponding output file
for i in range(len(input_files)):
    input_file = input_files[i]
    preprocessed_file = preprocessed_files[i]

    # Open input file and preprocessed file for writing
    with open(input_file, 'r', encoding='latin-1') as f, \
        open(preprocessed_file, 'w', newline='',
encoding='utf-8') as f2:

        # Create a CSV reader and writer objects
        reader = csv.reader(f)
        writer = csv.writer(f2)

        # Iterate over each row in the input file
        for row in reader:
            # Convert to lowercase
            row = [word.lower() for word in row]

            # Join row elements to form a single string
            row = ' '.join(row)

            # Replace dash with space and remove punctuation
            row = row.replace('-', ' ')
            row = row.translate(str.maketrans('', '', string.punctuation))

            # Remove numbers
            row = re.sub(r'\d+', '', row)

            # Tokenize and remove stop words
            tokens = word_tokenize(row)
            tokens = [word for word in tokens if not word in
stop_words]

            # Write preprocessed data to file
            writer.writerow(tokens)

    # Open preprocessed file for reading and frequency count
file for writing
    with open(preprocessed_files[i], 'r', encoding='utf-8')
as f, \
        open(frequency_files[i], 'w', newline='',
encoding='utf-8') as f2:

        # Create a CSV reader and writer objects
        reader = csv.reader(f)
        writer = csv.writer(f2)

```

```

        # Count frequency of appearance of each token
        frequency = Counter()
        for row in reader:
            frequency.update(row)

        # Write frequency count data to file
        writer.writerow(['Token', 'Frequency'])
        for token, count in frequency.items():
            writer.writerow([token, count])

    print(f"Processed file {i+1}/{len(input_files)}")

print('The process is over')

```

CODE 7-19: This code is used to filter out any tokens not found in DATAvoc.
Steps:

1. It imports the csv module, for reading and writing CSV files.
2. It defines a list `input_files` containing the filenames of the 19 reviewers.
3. It defines a variable `words_input_file` containing DATAvoc.
4. It defines a list `output_files` containing the filenames for the result with word frequencies.
5. The code enters a loop to process each input file in `input_files`. In each iteration: a. It creates an empty dictionary `freq_dict` to store word frequencies. b. It opens the current input file and reads its content using the `csv.reader` function. The header row is skipped. c. It iterates over each row in the input file and stores the word frequencies in the `freq_dict` dictionary. The word is the value in the first column, and the frequency is the integer value in the second column of each row.
6. The code continues in the loop and opens the corresponding output file using the `open` function with the filename from `output_files[i]`. It writes the header row, containing the column names 'Word' and 'Frequency', using the `csv.writer` function and the `writerow` method.
7. It opens the `words_input_file` and reads its content using `csv.reader`. For each row in the file, it checks if the word is present in the `freq_dict` dictionary. If the word is found, it retrieves its frequency from the dictionary; otherwise, it assigns a frequency of 0.
8. It writes the word and its frequency as a row in the output file using the `writer.writerow` method.
9. The loop continues until all input files are processed.
10. Finally, it prints the message "The process is over" to indicate that the process is complete.

```

import csv

# Define input and output filenames
input_files = ['N1_frequency.csv', 'N2_frequency.csv',
               'N3_frequency.csv', 'N4_frequency.csv', 'N5_frequency.csv',
               'N6_frequency.csv', 'N7_frequency.csv', 'N8_frequency.csv',

```

```

'N9_frequency.csv', 'N10_frequency.csv', 'N11_frequency.csv',
'N12_frequency.csv', 'N13_frequency.csv',
'N14_frequency.csv', 'N15_frequency.csv',
'N16_frequency.csv', 'N17_frequency.csv',
'N18_frequency.csv', 'N19_frequency.csv']
words_input_file = 'DATAvoc.csv'
output_files = ['N1_DATAvoc.csv', 'N2_DATAvoc.csv',
'N3_DATAvoc.csv', 'N4_DATAvoc.csv', 'N5_DATAvoc.csv',
'N6_DATAvoc.csv', 'N7_DATAvoc.csv', 'N8_DATAvoc.csv',
'N9_DATAvoc.csv', 'N10_DATAvoc.csv', 'N11_DATAvoc.csv',
'N12_DATAvoc.csv', 'N13_DATAvoc.csv', 'N14_DATAvoc.csv',
'N15_DATAvoc.csv', 'N16_DATAvoc.csv', 'N17_DATAvoc.csv',
'N18_DATAvoc.csv', 'N19_DATAvoc.csv']

# Loop through input files
for i, input_file in enumerate(input_files):
    # Create a dictionary to store word frequencies
    freq_dict = {}

    # Read vocabulary file and store word frequencies in the
    dictionary
    with open(input_file, 'r') as file:
        reader = csv.reader(file)
        next(reader) # skip header row
        for row in reader:
            freq_dict[row[0]] = int(row[1])

    # Open output file and write header row
    with open(output_files[i], 'w', newline='') as file:
        writer = csv.writer(file)
        writer.writerow(['Word', 'Frequency'])

    # Read words file and write word frequencies to
    output file
    with open(words_input_file, 'r') as words_file:
        reader = csv.reader(words_file)
        for row in reader:
            word = row[0]
            if word in freq_dict:
                freq = freq_dict[word]
            else:
                freq = 0
            writer.writerow([word, freq])
print('The process is over')
```

Comparison Spreadsheet link:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1nvjuATYk8eXEF40aXzymIH1jS0d6P87/edit?usp=sharing&oid=104493436601510445237&rtpof=true&sd=true>

The results for the nineteen reviewers are in worksheets N1 to N19 of the Comparison Spreadsheet above. Below is a sample for reviewer No1:

TOKEN	FREQUENCY	WAW	final WAW	WSET	final WSET	Comparison	N1 (DATAvoc)	WAW	final WAW	WSET	final WSET	WAW/WSET	NULL
abrasive	96	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
acacia	254	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
acai	22	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
acetic	7	YES	YES	NO	NO	WAW	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
acetone	2	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
acid	624	YES	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
acidic	462	NO	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
acidity	24597	NO	YES	YES	YES	WAW/WSET	97	0	97	97	97	97	0
acids	243	NO	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
afterburn	1	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
afternotes	2	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
aftertaste	1456	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
age	3247	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ageability	26	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ageable	3	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
aged	153	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
ageing	1	NO	NO	YES	YES	WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ageless	1	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ageworthiness	3	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ageworthy	140	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
aggression	1	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
aggressive	218	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
aggressiveness	2	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
aging	22	NO	NO	NO	YES	WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
aid	99	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
aids	2	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
alcohol	856	YES	YES	YES	YES	WAW/WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
alcoholic	72	NO	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
alfalfa	5	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
alkaline	5	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
alkalinity	2	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
allium	3	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
alloro	3	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
allspice	131	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
almond	1625	YES	YES	YES	YES	WAW/WSET	3	3	3	3	3	3	0
almonds	105	NO	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
almondy	2	NO	YES	NO	YES	WAW/WSET	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
aloe	5	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
alpha	7	NO	NO	NO	NO	NULL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0